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A review of the policy and economic landscape in rural Scotland: informing plausible and aspirational scenarios

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Introduction

The Scottish Government funds a five year Strategic Research Programme (2022-27) through the Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services (RESAS) Division to advance the evidence base in the development of rural affairs, food and environment policies.

One of the themes of the research programme is on Rural Futures. This theme has three research topics: rural communities, rural economy and land reform. There are two projects within each topic led by Scotland's Rural College and the James Hutton Institute. This publication sits within this theme. Within the rural economy topic, the two projects are titled:

'Informing a socially and spatially just future for the Scottish rural economy: pinpointing opportunities, assets and support needs'

'Novel insights on Scotland's rural and island economies'

The first project, led by the James Hutton Institute, aims to use mixed methods to create an advanced, holistic understanding of the Scottish rural economy and the diversity of responses to multiple crises and events across rural Scotland, in the context of national objectives to deliver a wellbeing economy and longer-term challenges of inequality and depopulation. We aim to identify and inform better interventions and approaches to local development which can enable positive changes in communities.

This piece of work aims to identify critical drivers of rural change which are described within recent peer-reviewed literature and technical reports. These drivers of change will be evaluated and used to inform the basis of *plausible scenarios* - in other words, likely futures - that could occur in rural areas if these drivers continue to follow current trends.

To produce these plausible scenarios, we are using the DEPEST (Demography, Economy, Policy and Governance, Environment, Society and Technology) framework, to draw out relevant themes from the literature. The DEPEST categories of 'macro-trends' affecting places has been applied successfully in rural scenario planning (Piras et al., 2022, drawing on work by Aguilar, 1967) and provides a clear framework and structure for identifying and understanding the major drivers of change affecting rural areas.

This framework aims to classify the key influences on the rural economy and on rural communities in a way that will help to identify opportunities, mitigate risks and better align future strategies with external realities. In this paper, we use the framework to identify plausible scenarios for rural and island areas of Scotland. Breaking down analysis into these categories allows for an in-depth examination of different aspects of rural experiences and helps to paint a more holistic image of plausible futures for rural and island communities. The scenarios are not a complete model of the future and are instead a speculation on potential futures

based on the projecting forward of past patterns and the likely effects of current circumstances and policies (Piras et al., 2022:8). The DEPEST categories used in this review are shown below (Table 1):

Table 1: Descriptions of the DEPEST drivers of rural change

Driver	Description
Demographic	Population trends and characteristics such as age structures, migration trends and the ‘push’ and ‘pull’ factors associated with rural areas
Economic	External factors with impacts on the rural economy including COVID-19 and the EU exit, and local economic characteristics, including income distributions, other inequalities and important industries
Policy and Governance	Government policy and how it relates to rural areas, and governance structures that exist in rural areas.
Environmental	Ecological and sustainability issues, including the role that rural areas play in facing climate change, how resource scarcity could impact on rural areas, and the green technologies that may offer solutions.
Society	Cultural aspects of rural areas, how people relate to rural areas in Scotland, and levels of health and mental health amongst rural populations
Technology	Exploring the disparities of technological advancement in Scotland, with rural areas often being left behind, and innovations that may change this trend.

Methodology

This piece of research has been carried out as a desk-based review which develops six short papers reflecting the six DEPEST drivers of rural change (Demography, Economy, Policy and Governance, Environment, Society, Technology) for the context of Scotland in 2025. To do this, we conducted a targeted literature search using the Web of Science Core Collection, specifying a “post-COVID-19” timespan. We did not have a defined future timescale for these scenarios. Literature searches used the Abstract and Author Keywords fields. Additional reading on these drivers was identified through snowballing, until a point where data saturation was reached and limited new insights were being revealed.

Search terms were as follows:

- Population Decline + Rural Scotland

- Future of rural communities + Rural Scotland
- Environment + Rural Scotland
- Transport + rural Scotland
- Technology + Rural Scotland
- Youth + Rural Scotland
- Social Capital + Rural Scotland
- Tourism + Rural Scotland
- Rural Business + Rural Scotland
- Healthcare + Rural Scotland
- Rural Policy + Rural Scotland
- Education + Rural Scotland

Titles and abstracts were screened on searching, and any that did not meet the location or topic criteria were not pursued. Those that met these initial criteria were then saved into a spreadsheet, where they were numbered, and the DEPEST drivers that they were relevant to were identified. We began with 41 articles. More articles were identified through snowballing and researcher discussions (an additional 19). On further reading, 10 more articles were discarded due to: not being in the study area, having an urban rather than rural focus, or not including enough relevant information in relation to the DEPEST drivers. A visual summary of this process is shown below (Figure 1). Note that Figure 1 does not include references which have been added to the review at the editing stage. Additionally, we utilise information collected as part of qualitative engagement on the rural economy and rural communities, and data summaries and analysis from the Scottish Government's Scottish Islands Survey (2023), to add further information on the drivers.

At the end of this review, we summarise a set of 'nexuses of change' (Piras et al., 2022: 960) – topics and questions which are critical for future patterns of economic development in rural Scotland. These are to be further discussed and refined with stakeholders and policymakers. Finally, as a contrast with the 'realistic' or 'business as usual' rural trends evaluated through the DEPEST drivers, a separate literature review of key rural policies and strategies has taken place to identify aspirational scenarios, and this is summarised at the end of the report. This information was collected as further analysis could consider the hypothetical effects of maximising and expanding the impacts of successful policies.

Figure 1: Summary of the literature review process for identifying plausible scenarios

Key Findings: DEPEST categories

Driver 1: Demography

Population trends and characteristics such as age structures, migration trends and the 'push' and 'pull' factors associated with rural areas.

- Rural Scotland has an unbalanced age structure, with an ageing and declining population.
- Outmigration occurs in many rural and island areas and is predominantly seen through young adults leaving their rural area to take up further education and job opportunities that aren't offered in their rural areas.
- Research suggests that more young people are considering returning home, largely due to the high costs of living in urban areas. However, the limited employment opportunities in rural and island areas create a difficult job market.
- Access to greenspaces, nature, the perceived quality of life and the opportunity to work remotely in rural and island areas are attractive options for those who wish to move or return to rural areas.
- The pressure of housing in rural Scotland is increasing as people are purchasing second homes and those at retirement age are moving to rural areas, 'pricing out' young people and those who are looking to move for work.
- Workers for key sectors such as education and healthcare are high in demand. However, in rural and island areas, these occupations often place additional pressure on workers. This may mean individuals seek extra training before taking up the role or the pressure may result in the occupation being off-putting.
- The combination of migration trends and the ageing population can place public services under increasing pressure and impact on community sustainability.

Driver 2: Economy

External factors with impacts on the rural economy including COVID-19 and the EU exit, and local economic characteristics, including income distributions, other inequalities and important industries.

- Part-time work, self-employment and small businesses are more common in rural areas than in urban areas. Those living in the Scottish islands are more likely to work in more than one paid job compared to the rest of Scotland.
- The current shrinking and ageing population is affecting labour markets and efforts to retain and attract workforces are needed.
- Some rural areas are currently seeing a decline in job and educational opportunities. Employment opportunities are harder to access in rural areas and there is difficulty in finding good quality employment opportunities with

sufficient pay and progression opportunities for those who return from urban areas.

- There are income inequalities between those living in accessible rural areas compared to those who live in remote rural areas.
- Austerity measures have led to service cuts in rural areas, causing services to become centralised leading to difficulties for rural residents.
- COVID-19 further worsened the labour market and housing challenges, particularly affecting the tourism and hospitality sectors.
- The cost-of-living crisis creates a challenge in the transition to a circular economy. People are more focused on purchasing affordable items from cheaper retailers than making long-term purchases.

Driver 3: Policy and Governance

Government policy and how it relates to rural areas, and governance structures that exist in rural areas.

- Recently, Scottish policy has shifted towards place-based policies, allowing them to better address the unique and specific features of rural areas and community needs. Typologies such as the Gow Typology (Gow, 2023) can be helpful when developing these place-based policies as they can help to differentiate between different types of rural areas.
- Community empowerment is encouraged by the Scottish Government, promoting community ownership and community involvement in risk management. However, a challenge faced by community groups is that the burden can fall on key individuals and groups within the local community and can be dependent on the level of expertise and time they have.
- The prioritisation of rural community well-being is being considered in Scotland through looking into 20-minute neighbourhoods and through the importance of community-led tourism.
- Centralised governance (Scotland or UK) often fails to cater to rural areas and is unable to distribute resources effectively. Local governance, however, struggles to have enough resources to support communities.

Driver 4: Environment

Ecological and sustainability issues, including the role that rural areas play in facing climate change, how resource scarcity could impact on rural areas, and the green technologies that may offer solutions.

- To meet the Scottish Government's net zero by 2045 target, the land management practices which are incentivised (for example, tree-planting and peatland restoration) provide challenges and opportunities for rural areas.
- Rewilding is an activity that can be part of green land investment and while it is a controversial term, it can potentially coexist with re-peopling to revitalise rural areas.

- Renewable energy efforts remain controversial with the challenges of balancing the environment and ecological preservation with the need for sustainable energy.
- The Climate Challenge Fund is an initiative by the Scottish Government that allows support to community climate change initiatives, however the impacts are often limited by community capacities.
- Community connections to land through crofting, cultural heritage projects and community land trusts develop ties to land, creating social capital within communities and improve community wellbeing.
- It is important to address the transport and infrastructure challenges in rural areas (public transport, electric car infrastructure and recycling opportunities) to support the transition to a circular economy.

Driver 5: Society

Cultural aspects of rural areas, how people relate to rural areas in Scotland, and levels of health and mental health amongst rural populations.

- Rural Scotland's current depopulation trend can be largely attributed to young people leaving for education and job opportunities in urban areas, with many not returning.
- Tourism is a key feature of many rural communities. Some view tourism positively: tourists potentially move to rural areas which can strengthen rural communities, bringing new ideas and activism. Challenges also arise, like increased traffic and travel disruption and environmental issues.
- Well-being in rural areas varies, with some studies indicating that rural areas have better well-being due to social cohesion and access to nature while some indicating well-being is worsened due to social isolation.
- Arts and culture are important in rural communities both through supporting business retention and maintaining populations.
- Post-primary educational opportunities are a concern in many rural areas. There is a need to address these challenges to support the provision of education to meet the needs of rural communities and to ensure sustainable community development.

Driver 6: Technology

Exploring the disparities of technological advancement in Scotland, with rural areas often being left behind, and innovations that may change this trend.

- Poor internet connections pose a significant challenge in rural Scotland. Issues such as connectivity speeds and the lack of up-to-date broadband infrastructure are faced in rural areas due to their remoteness and low population density.
- Top-down policy-led approaches seek to address the rural-urban digital divide including broadband connectivity; however, these approaches have been

criticised for being overly centralised and for not addressing the specific broadband issues in rural areas. Community-based approaches also seek to improve digital access in rural areas; however, these often require major commitments from rural residents.

- Technological advancements in transport and healthcare offer potential benefits to rural communities, however infrastructure to support these must be addressed first.
- The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the importance of digitalisation and provided the opportunity for remote work, which positively impacted rural employment and resilience.

Driver 1: Demography

Scotland has an increasingly unbalanced age structure: Leith and Sim (2022: 2) state that data from the National Records of Scotland indicates in the last 20 years the number of those aged 65 and over has increased by 32%, whereas the number of people below 18 years of age has decreased by 7%. Since the late 2000's there has been a population decline in many remote rural areas, with sparse and remote areas particularly affected, while more accessible rural areas closer to urban centres are experiencing population growth (Scottish Government, 2022:24-25). Population expansion is predicted for many of Scotland's urban areas, whereas most rural and island areas are predicted to have population declines.

The demography section will highlight the key drivers that are influencing the population of rural Scotland: rural to urban migration, counter-urbanisation, the impact the EU exit has had on migration, and Scotland's ageing population.

Rural-urban migration

Outmigration is an issue that is faced by many islands and rural areas and is particularly age specific (Scottish Government, 2022). Research has demonstrated imbalances in the rural population partly due to the migration of young people seeking higher education or other job opportunities in urban settings (Maclaren et al., 2024; Tent et al., 2023). Accessibility to further education can be one of the deciding factors of people staying or leaving a rural area (Tent et al., 2023). The trend of young people leaving to pursue higher education in urban areas reinforces the ageing population and depopulation of rural regions (Tent et al., 2023).

Some young adults seek jobs that can lead back to their rural communities, in key sectors such as healthcare and education. However, the pressured work environments they are likely to face in rural areas encourage some to delay their return in order to pursue additional training (Alexander, 2023). Others highlighted the idea that in the past, young people in rural areas felt they had to move away in order to achieve a successful life (Clarke, 2021) and often would not return after finding employment or would return later on in life. However, this idea appears to be changing. Clarke (2021) demonstrates that young people are increasingly valuing the opportunity to stay in their region. Data from The

Scottish Islands Survey (2023) supports this, with 79% of respondents aged 18-35 agreeing that they were most likely to stay in their island for the next 5 years, an increase from 71% in the 2020 survey (Wilson et al., 2024:12).

People who do return as graduates will have different skills and knowledge that may not be suited to the demands in rural areas (Tent et al., 2023). A lack of stable jobs with salaries sufficient for the cost of living in a city can play a role in graduates returning home, in order to save money while living with family (Alexander, 2023). There are challenges, however, with returning home after education as it can be difficult to progress in desired careers due to the rural location and limited access to opportunities (Alexander, 2023).

The University of the Highland and Islands

The University of the Highlands and Islands is a 'decentralised educational institution' in Scotland and is a key example of a 'post-school educational opportunity' that offers those who want to seek further education opportunities a space to do so without having to move outside their rural area (Tent et al., 2023). It is also seen as a way to attract people to rural areas who are interested in specific, more specialised courses that are offered. In doing this, it offers further social benefits and provides opportunities for education, both which improve quality of life. Tent et al. (2023) state that it is critical to have institutions like this in rural areas facing demographic challenges and in areas with logistical difficulties as they contribute to regional development, employment opportunities, supporting communities and infrastructure development.

Counter urbanisation

Several rural areas are desirable places to live due to the quality of their environment. The idea of a rural idyll is described as "a vivid concept in the popular imagination (which) plays an important role in urban to rural migration, motivating people to move from a city to the country in search of a better life" (Wilson, Noble and Currie, 2025:1). Research has found that there are many factors that attract people to rural areas including the picturesque landscape; a strong sense of community; and seeking a positive work-life balance (Maclaren et al., 2024:2). The Scottish Islands Survey (2023) demonstrates that 41% of islanders who moved or returned to their island, moved for a better lifestyle or quality of life (Wilson et al., 2024:11).

Many people living in cities perceived rural areas as a haven during the COVID-19 pandemic which encouraged people to make the move to rural areas during that period, either for the first time or to second homes (Wilson, Noble and Currie, 2025). Rural areas were perceived as safer, with less chance of exposure to COVID-19, providing open and accessible greenspaces that contrasted with

cities (Wilson, Noble and Currie 2025). Although urban to rural migration can help to reverse depopulation in rural areas, there are also negative repercussions. For example, research demonstrates that though doctors may move to rural areas to work in a close-knit team and maintain a better work-life balance, the reality is often a large workload falling on one doctor, due to difficulties in recruiting and retaining staff (Scottish Government, 2022).

Another form of counter-urbanisation is through pre-retirement or retirement migration. There is evidence that many older people choose to migrate to rural areas either during the pre-retirement or retirement stage of their lives (Maclaren et al., 2024). Those in the pre-retirement stage make up a high percentage of people moving to rural areas. People choose to move for many reasons, including lifestyle changes and wanting a change or challenge in their daily life (Maclaren et al., 2024). This increases the imbalance of the population and can add strain on over-stretched rural services such as healthcare (Maclaren et al., 2024).

The pressure of housing on Rural Scotland

Movement to rural areas after COVID-19 has led to additional pressures put on the housing market. The purchasing of second homes decreases available houses, raises prices, and prevents people from moving to work and live in rural communities. Digitalisation can allow for remote working but doesn't fulfil key roles in the community; connectivity issues and poor infrastructure (see Technology section) can mean that population shifts often aren't permanent (Wilson, Noble and Currie, 2025). Wilson, Noble and Currie (2025: 6) demonstrated that young people feel that they have been "priced out of the market" as a result of counter-urbanisation from the COVID-19 pandemic. Due to tourism and the purchase of holiday-lets and second homes, prices are affecting the sustainability of rural communities. In some Highland rural communities, networks are deteriorating, and generational divisions are becoming more apparent (White, van Melik, Bendle, 2024: 932). Concerns have been raised that the trend of those moving from urban areas to rural areas will increase, and that the pressures on housing will worsen, leaving younger people with reduced opportunities to access housing and jobs (Currie et al., 2024).

The impact of EU exit on Rural Scotland's population

The EU exit raised concerns over its impacts on the demographics and economies of rural Scotland. In 2022, it was described as the 'greatest threat' to population growth and migration to Scotland (Leith and Sim, 2022: 3), and similar views were raised for rural populations and employees in the UK (Neal et al., 2021). Indeed, the EU exit has contributed to reduced migration to Scotland from countries in the east of the EU (Brzozowska-Rup and Radowicz, 2025). Woods (2023: 1) provides a summary of the critical challenges of the EU exit: "...new barriers to trade, uncertainties over funding for agriculture and for community development, and the changed status of EU migrant workers".

Scotland's Ageing Population

Migration to rural areas – such as counter-urbanisation, described above – has not in many cases been sufficient to lead to population growth. Rural Scotland has an ageing and declining population (Scottish Government, 2022; McIntyre and Roy, 2023; Maclaren et al., 2024) with Scotland’s whole population projected to decline over the next 25 years (Leith and Sim, 2022). Analysis completed by the Scottish Government suggests that the aging population comes from a natural rise in life expectancy but is ameliorated by those in a pre-retirement or retirement stage migrating to rural areas. Many rural areas are experiencing reduced services in ‘health, social care, and education’, and alongside the ageing population, this has been shown to worsen service provision and leads to further difficulties in recruiting healthcare staff (Maclaren et al., 2024: 1). During the COVID-19 pandemic there was a particular worry in rural areas about the strain this put on already constrained health services (McIntyre and Roy, 2023). Consequently, there is a rising age imbalance due to an expanding population of retirees migrating to rural areas and a decrease in ‘children and working age adults below the Scottish average’ population (Scottish Government, 2022:25).

Conclusion

This section has focused on Driver 1: Demography. The population of rural Scotland is aging and declining, and will continue to do so unless adequate affordable housing and viable career pathways are made available to young people wanting to remain or return to rural areas. Remote working opportunities and higher education openings, such as the UHI initiative outlined above, and easier access to green spaces and nature pose attractive options to some young adults wanting to return, and those wishing to migrate to rural areas. Research suggests that more young people are considering returning home, largely due to the high costs of living in urban areas. However, the nature of employment in rural and island areas creates a difficult job market. Workers for key sectors such as education and healthcare are high in demand, and those who are able to work fully remotely also have viable and secure career options. However, the pressure these key sectors can put on individuals in rural and island areas may require extra training or be off-putting to those wanting to return. Continued efforts to ensure career pathways for young people wanting to stay in or return to rural and island areas could result in a growing population. However, the housing crisis must be sufficiently addressed; as an increase in pre-retirement and retired populations, as well as second home owners, drives house prices up. The combination of these trends of migration and population aging can place public services under increasing pressure and impact on community sustainability.

Driver 2: Economy

Employment

Although the land-based sectors of agriculture, forestry and fishing are still important to the rural economy, their importance has reduced over time (Dalglish et al., 2020:51). Sectors that create higher levels of employment in rural areas are ‘public administration, education and health’; ‘distribution, transport, accommodation and food’ services; and manufacturing and real estate services

too. Hospitality (hotels and restaurants) and banking and finance are also significant employers in rural areas (Dalglish et al., 2020:50-51). In sparsely populated rural areas, the service industry is very important for the economy, making up 73% of employment.

Part-time roles, self-employment and residents owning small businesses are more common in rural areas compared to urban areas (Dalglish et al., 2020). Data from the Scottish Islands Survey (2023) also demonstrates that people living in the Scottish Islands are more likely to work more than one paid job (28%) compared to the rest of Scotland (Wilson et al. 2024: 16).

Renewable energy is providing new employment opportunities for the Scottish islands, which have resources that have the potential to supply some of the UK's electricity demand and generate income for island economies. There are blue economy opportunities such as 'offshore wind, wave and tidal energy'. Scotland's islands are also excellent locations for space launches - for example in North Uist and Shetland - which could lead to a large share of the 'global space economy' (Islands Growth Deal, 2023:8).

Over the years to come, the shrinking and ageing population of rural and island areas, as outlined above, is going to have an effect on the labour market. The Islands Growth Deal projects that there will be '7,100 job openings in the islands between 2024 and 2031.' As a result, there will need to be a focus on retaining and also attracting employees in already existent sectors (Islands Growth Deal, 2023: 10).

Sustainable and Good Quality Employment

Despite some projections of growth in employment, as noted above, currently rural areas are seeing a decline in employment opportunities as well as having more limited career and education opportunities (Clarke, 2021; Dalglish et al., 2020). Employment opportunities have been identified as hard to access for young people; and a lack of jobs with sufficient incomes or career progression creates a difficult job market for those returning to rural or island communities from urban areas (Dalglish et al., 2020:51; Vercher et al., 2021: 172; Alexander, 2023: 5). Many young people are having to make compromises to live in their rural community, mostly around transport and the lack of job opportunities (Clarke, 2021: 143-144). Research suggests that young people want to stay in or move to island areas, however, there is a need for good quality jobs with adequate pay and progression opportunities, alongside available housing and a low cost of living (Islands Growth Deal 2023: 9).

In research led by Dolton-Thornton (2021:42), Scottish Highland land managers highlighted in interviews that a 'robust economy' is needed to help facilitate 'successful repopulation' and the importance of a job being nearby their lives/home. To create a more resilient economy there is the need to create local jobs, and raise levels of 'entrepreneurship and business diversification, investment and quality of work' (McIntyre and Roy, 2023: 2). On the other hand, there have also been issues with recruiting staff for both low-skilled and high-

skilled professional jobs in rural areas (Dalglish et al., 2020). One potential explanation for this is because of the COVID-19 pandemic occurring not long after EU exit (McIntyre and Roy, 2023: 8).

Regional and income inequalities

A Scottish policy focus has been on city-region deals as there is the view that economic growth is driven by cities (Clelland, 2020). However, there has been a change in policy towards 'inclusive growth,' to include all areas and regions, making the development fairer (Clelland, 2020: 22). Additionally, as a result of its involvement in regional deals and other initiatives, the UK Government has become more involved in regional economic development in Scotland over time (Clelland, 2024).

Many inequalities (poverty, deprivation) were apparent in the years following the global financial crisis and the great recession from 2007-2009. In the UK there is an unequal regional spread of poverty and deprivation, resulting in some places being deemed 'left behind' (Clelland, 2021: 155). Targeting poverty in rural areas is difficult to do as deprivation in rural areas tends to be less spatially concentrated compared with urban deprivation, and therefore the measures used to assess deprivation, such as the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation, are not as suitable for rural areas (Clelland, 2021). Local governments aiming to deliver services and make decisions based on area-specific needs have also experienced budget cuts (Clelland, 2021: 155).

The Scottish Government's '[Rural Planning to 2050](#)' report describes the income inequalities faced between regions and rural areas (Dalglish et al., 2020). It states that those who live in more accessible rural areas have the 'highest average incomes' while those who live in remote rural areas 'have the lowest'. One reason that could explain this is the distance to a city or urban area, as often higher earning commuters will live in more accessible areas. Those who live in remote rural areas need a higher income (compared to those who live in more accessible areas) to achieve an equivalent standard of living due to additional costs of fuel, food and other necessities (Dalglish et al., 2020: 53).

Cuts to services leading to centralisation

Austerity has increased the difficulties that have been faced by rural areas of Scotland, in particular having an effect on younger people and other 'vulnerable groups' (Clelland, 2021: 158). Rural areas often experience cuts to their services, which has led to limited services or loss of services or facilities altogether. Common facilities that have been reduced in rural communities in Great Britain are schools, libraries, healthcare facilities and pubs which are often locations where residents meet and are important spaces for them (Woods, 2023: 5-6). The centralisation of services causes difficulties for rural residents and means residents have to travel longer distances to access services (Dalglish et al., 2020) and due to government cuts, local authorities are often having to cut services, leading to more services being centralised (Dalglish et al., 2020). An interviewee in one study highlighted their concerns about urbanisation, and the

additional pressure that is placed on services in accessible rural areas due to their closeness to 'towns and cities' (Dalglish et al., 2020:55). The cuts in services often leave communities to find solutions in order to keep services running, which puts additional burdens on them and creates inequalities due to the different capacities that communities have to respond (Dalglish et al., 2020: 54, 57, 80). Other interviewees spoke about the issues with transport services being affected, running limited services or in some cases stopping bus services entirely, which has a knock-on impact on health outcomes leading to isolation (Dalglish et al., 2020: 80). Not having connections to services also negatively affects local businesses due to an impact on their workforce and customers (Dalglish et al., 2020). Overall, the increasing centralisation of services – to larger towns and cities, and in the accessible commuter zones surrounding them – has a negative impact on rural areas and may cause people to leave rural communities.

Impact of COVID-19 on rural economies

The COVID-19 crisis occurred shortly after the UK left the European Union which in turn worsened the labour market, with further challenges with recruitment, across many job types (McIntyre and Roy, 2023: 8). There have been persistent housing challenges in rural areas and due to the pandemic, interviewees from a research study led by McIntyre and Roy (2023: 8) highlighted concerns over the increasing demand for second homes and holiday lets during this time - this in turn has affected job recruitment. Tourism and hospitality were two sectors that were heavily impacted due to the pandemic and which both play large roles in the rural economy (McIntyre and Roy, 2023). Due to the reliance on tourism and hospitality industries, when the pandemic arrived, many businesses had to close, leading to loss of jobs and income (Glass et al., 2023: 57). Many people had to seek additional employment, taking up second jobs. Some businesses however, decided to stay open to keep their economic activities up and to ensure some regularity and normalcy during an unprecedented time (McIntyre and Roy, 2023: 6).

COVID-19 did have perceived positive outcomes for some rural communities in Scotland too. In research led by Currie et al. (2024: 36-37), interviewees suggested that the pandemic allowed working from home to become more normalised and presented an opportunity for repopulation in rural and island areas, creating employment opportunities and encouraging young people to stay and move to rural and island areas. Data from The Scottish Islands Survey (2023) demonstrated that over one quarter of respondents work from home either some or most of the time (Wilson et al., 2024:13). Rural areas being seen as a safe place during the COVID-19 pandemic led to an urban to rural migration which provided the potential to repopulate some rural areas. This effect has however also had negative outcomes on rural communities, for example by amplifying the inequalities in some communities and increasing the difficulty of finding places to house key workers in the community (Wilson, Noble and Currie: 2025). Overall, it is uncertain whether migration linked to the COVID-19 pandemic has actually had long-term effects on the rural population of Scotland.

Circular Economy

The circular economy is the notion that we move from a “take, make, dispose” mindset to a model of us ‘valuing materials and keeping them in use’ (Scottish Government, 2024: 5). The Scottish Circular Economy bill was passed in June 2024 and became an Act, a few months later in August 2024.

The cost-of-living crisis creates a challenge to transitioning to a more circular economy. Evidence suggests that people are more focused on buying affordable items from cheaper retailers, than making purchases for the long term, and it is difficult to promote the circular economy and sustainability when people are struggling with costs (Malcolm, Macaulay and Todd, 2024). Schemes such as the

Scottish Government’s proposed deposit return scheme have been criticised as adding additional costs onto those who are already experiencing the cost-of-living crisis the most, and some rural residents even end up traveling further distances to access big supermarkets, or choose to purchase items online, rather than buying local produce (Malcolm, Macaulay and Todd, 2024: 6).

Tourism

Tourism plays a key role in the economy of rural and island areas. White, van Melik and Bendle (2024: 918) state that tourism accounted for 20,000 jobs just in the Highlands as of 2019. Rural communities view some aspects of tourism positively, due to the economic benefits such as through the creation of jobs for local businesses (White, van Melik and Bendle, 2024). Some believe that there are inequalities in the economic benefits that tourism brings to communities, for example economic development favouring places already marketed as popular tourism destinations (White, van Melik and Bendle, 2024). Furthermore, some Highland communities do not feel that they are consulted when it comes to making decisions and identify negative impacts on the environment (White, van Melik and Bendle, 2024). The Scottish Islands Survey (Wilson et al., 2024:13) also demonstrated that many islanders viewed the impacts of tourism positively, however a majority of respondents disagreed that there was sufficient infrastructure for tourism, with one participant highlighting how they were no longer able to access their own attractions in Orkney due to them being fully booked by tourists.

Tourists have also been heavily influenced by media through popular films, books and TV shows based in Scotland, which has created considerable income for the Scottish economy (Garrison and Wallace, 2021). Opposed to the negativity that some people have towards tourists, there have also been examples of media tourists who work to create their own tours from a book, show or film. Some have worked with organisations to encourage considerate tourism (Garrison and Wallace, 2021). One example is the Outlander novels and TV programme, where fans created a map along with the community in Inverness for other fans to follow, supporting the local community and businesses (Garrison and Wallace, 2021: 8-9).

The North Coast 500 has also been a big contributor to the economy in the Highlands. It was created by the North Highland Initiative who aim to promote 'regional economic growth' (White, van Melik and Bendle, 2024: 925). The aim was to link tourist sights together in a loop, and this resulted in income of £9 million and attracting 29,000 visitors in its first year (White, van Melik and Bendle, 2024: 925). COVID-19 heavily impacted the tourism and hospitality industries which are crucial for many rural communities (McIntyre and Roy, 2023). Tourism saw a growth in 'virtual tours' post lockdown, where there was a restriction on people travelling (Garrison and Wallace, 2021: 8-9). The virtual tours supported the guidance of staying at home but promoted and encouraged people to visit in the future (Garrison and Wallace, 2021: 9-10). There have been questions about whether people should pay for this kind of content and Garrison and Wallace (2021:10) suggest that there is a need for future research to develop 'sustainable business models' for virtual tourism.

As mentioned, tourism plays a vital role in the rural economy, however, lately there has been emphasis on the extractive nature of tourism and concerns over tourism's sustainability as well as the lack of infrastructure to support tourism. Alternative models of tourism are now also emerging, such as virtual tours (largely implemented due to COVID-19) and media tourists who work with the community and local businesses to encourage visitors to support the local economy.

Conclusion

This section has focused on Driver 2: Economy. It highlights that part-time work, self-employment, and small businesses are more common in rural areas compared to urban ones. Renewable energy is creating new job opportunities, and the islands have potential in the global space economy. However, the shrinking and aging population will impact the labour market in the long-term, necessitating efforts to retain and attract employees.

Despite projected growth, rural areas of Scotland face declining employment opportunities and difficulties in recruiting staff, exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic and EU exit. Economic development has shifted towards a more place-based approach, focusing on cities, but there is a push for inclusive growth to address regional inequalities.

Austerity measures have led to cuts in services, centralizing them and causing difficulties for rural residents. The COVID-19 pandemic further worsened the labour market and housing challenges, particularly affecting tourism and hospitality sectors. The Scottish Government has outlined its aim of transitioning to a circular economy; however, the cost-of-living crisis has led people to prioritise affordability over sustainability. Overall, a recent period of multiple crises and major events has presented a significant challenge for the resilience of rural economies.

Driver 3: Policy and Governance

Scotland's approach to rural policy and governance reflects a transition from traditional, sector-focused measures towards more integrated and community-driven strategies. There has been an emphasis on local empowerment, sustainable development and collaborative action. Though this has attempted to redistribute some power, it is notable that it has put additional responsibilities onto already stretched rural community members, and often the burden of change falls disproportionately on a small number of key community figures.

This change in focus reflects a wider shift in understanding rural areas as 'diverse and complex socio-economic systems' with diversity between rural areas (OECD, 2018:21). A recent report by the Scottish Human Rights Commission indicates starkly that rural policies are not currently addressing rural needs, stating that food and housing provision are currently not meeting Minimum Core Obligations (SHRC, 2024:18).

As well as housing, current policy challenges include pressure on local services (especially health); reversing depopulation; more investment in digital infrastructure; increasing opportunities for local businesses; mobilising community groups and an increasing focus on natural capital and the natural economy (Atterton and Glass, 2021: 3-5). More broadly, since the creation of the Scottish Parliament and the Scottish Government following devolution, economic policies and strategies have increasingly recognised progressive and inclusive goals for economic development; however some researchers have suggested that these policies have not, in reality, moved away from a fundamental focus on economic growth (Clelland et al., 2024; Goudie et al., 2024). In this section, we explore key aspects of Scotland's rural policy and governance frameworks.

Place-Based Policies

Over the past two decades there has been a move towards place-based policies in Scotland, with efforts to better define the distinct features of rural areas (Philip et al., 2024:119). Early definitions defined rural as anything outside urban areas, or using criteria such as population density or agricultural land (Stjernberg et al., 2023:3). The urban-rural classification, introduced in 2003 by the Scottish Government, illustrates efforts to recognise the differences between urban and rural areas (Philip et al., 2024:114). Though this classification is still used in Scotland, research has demonstrated that a more nuanced approach is needed, especially to capture the unique challenges faced by remote areas, islands and sparsely populated areas (Scottish Government, 2020). The classification also results in 'small towns' often being excluded from rural statistics, despite the important role they play as a hub for services and employment for surrounding rural areas (Philip, Wilson and Duffy, 2024: 118). Research has found that Scottish governance arrangements are not 'well-adapted' to rural areas, with smaller communities unable to come up with the necessary resources themselves, and centralised governance structures unable to effectively distribute resources to these areas (Vercher et al., 2021: 173).

Place-based policies and approaches aim to address the needs of specific rural communities in a 'holistic' way (Scottish Government, 2020:17). In order to do this, the diversity between rural areas must be appreciated, and it has been suggested that different typologies could help to differentiate between rural areas (Scottish Government, 2020: 17). Existing typologies have been developed for a wide range of purposes and scales, using varied data from different contexts (Scottish Government, 2020:17). Recent typologies, such as the Gow typology (2023), offer a more nuanced overview of the islands in Scotland, emphasising that previous geographical typologies miss the heterogeneity of islands and the similarities between islands across different areas (Gow et al., 2023: 3). This has allowed localised issues, such as schooling, healthcare provision, grocery stores, fuel availability and ferry crossings to be scrutinised more closely, and has enabled islands to be identified by their level of independence and stability, rather than their location (Gow, 2023). Typologies like this which focus on societal indicators have allowed the development of more nuanced place-based policies (Dalglish et al., 2020). It has been recommended that, in order to support the creation of more place-based policies, the data used to develop these typologies should be incorporated into Local Development Plans and other localised plans and policies (Dalglish et al., 2020).

Community Empowerment

A dominant discourse at the national level, from the Scottish Government, encourages community empowerment and community ownership, with the UK government also encouraging an increase in 'responsibilisation', involving citizens in the risk management of their communities (Vercher et al., 2021: 176; Mackinnon, 2012: 257). However, this approach can place a disproportionate burden on a small number of active community members (Dolton-Thornton, 2021: 37). Additionally, increased community responsibility can absolve 'capital and the state from accountability' and normalises uneven development across economically varied communities (Mackinnon and Derickson, 2012: 263). Yet, substantial involvement of local individuals opens opportunities for 'participative democracy' and 'collective wellbeing', and some argue that this dispersal of power should go further and give the community property rights to certain areas of 'communal lands', to truly enable community empowerment (Dolton-Thornton, 2021: 37).

Following the move towards more place-based policies from the Scottish Government after devolution in 1999, was a set of legislation that supports the development and governance of third sector bodies (Slee, 2024: 4,9). Development Trusts in rural areas have been identified as 'anchor organisations' and indeed have been often mentioned in interviews carried out as part of this project's Living Labs, as key agents of change (Slee, 2024: 9). In some areas, it has been noted that development trusts that engage in private enterprise as well as communitarian action enable shifts of power (Slee, 2024:13). The Community Land Acts have similarly challenged the power of large landowners in Scotland, through the creation of strong platforms for community-led sustainable development (Slee, 2024:13). Community Wealth Building (CWB) is also emerging as an approach to local economic development, aiming to redirect

wealth back into the local economy and put control back into the hands of local people (Atterton and Glass, 2021: 23-24). Importantly, it has been highlighted by some that empowerment policies need to improve in order to go beyond simply being rhetoric (Henderson et al., 2020: 231-32). For example, in relation to flood resilience, genuine public consultation and providing long-term roles in decision-making for community members should reduce polarisation and ensure that local expertise is incorporated into responses to flooding, and climate change more broadly (Henderson et al., 2020: 231-232).

The prioritisation of community well-being

The Scottish Government's most recent National Planning Framework (Scottish Government, 2023) has promoted 20 minute neighbourhoods as a way of supporting sustainable communities and the liveability of places, the idea being that essential services for basic needs and wellbeing are reachable by all community members within 20 minutes (Atterton and Glass, 2021: 24). While noted as a particularly difficult achievement for many rural areas, it has been suggested that public transport links between villages will be vital in delivering this in rural communities (Atterton and Glass, 2021: 24).

Community well-being is also being discussed in relation to tourism (White, van Melik and Bendle, 2024: 934). One study, when researching the impacts of the North Coast 500 road trip route, found that the route was currently presented in such a way that excludes local communities along the route (White, van Melik and Bendle, 2024: 934). The study highlighted that the impact that tourism has on the identity of Highland communities must be considered and that community-led tourism planning is encouraged, to shape the experience of tourism in ways that support community well-being (White, van Melik and Bendle, 2024: 934). If tourism is to remain a central industry for rural economies, which it is likely to, it is crucial that local communities have a say in how it is managed.

More broadly, economic development policies for rural areas in many countries are increasingly pursuing broader wellbeing goals. For example, 'Rural Policy 3.0' was published by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in 2018, as a policy framework which aims to deliver 'a level of well-being to rural dwellers that is comparable to what is attainable in urban areas' (OECD, 2018: 21). Three dimensions of well-being were set out: economic, relying on productive and competitive employment; social dimensions that are made up of a cohesive and supportive community; and a pleasant local environment (OECD, 2018: 21).

Focus on the agricultural sector

The farming sector in Scotland has received subsidies, historically via the European Union's Common Agricultural Policy, and more recently from the national government. However, only a minority of funds have gone towards non-farming rural actors (Slee, 2024: 5).

Centralised Governance

A common theme within the literature review was the impact that centralised governance, whether at the level of Scotland or the whole of the UK, has on rural areas. For example, migration policy is formulated at Westminster despite the migration needs of parts of the UK, including Scotland, being different to those of London and Southern England (Leith and Sim, 2022: 2). The Brexit referendum was also enabled by the UK Government (Leith and Sim, 2022: 2). The results of the referendum have subsequently impacted Scottish demography and in-migration, making it harder for EU nationals to move to and work in Scotland (Leith and Sim, 2022: 3) and recent evidence supports the negative impact of Brexit on migration from Europe (Brzozowska-Rup and Radowicz, 2025). The effects have put a strain on the agricultural and hospitality sectors, which have previously relied heavily on an EU labour force (Leith and Sim, 2022: 3). Indeed, governance structures in Scotland have also been identified as unable to cater to rural particularities, with localised governance struggling to have enough resources, and centralised governance unable to distribute sufficient or effective resources (Vercher et al., 2021: 173).

Conclusion

This section focused on Driver 3: Policy and Governance. Over the past two decades, Scotland has shifted towards place-based policies to better define and address the unique features of rural areas. The urban-rural classification introduced in 2003 by the Scottish Government aimed to recognize differences between urban and rural areas, but research suggests that a more nuanced approach is needed, especially for remote and sparsely populated areas. Place-based policies aim to address the needs of specific rural communities holistically, appreciating the diversity between rural areas. Recent typologies have focused on societal indicators rather than physical ones, helping scrutinise local issues more closely and support the creation of more effective place-based policies. Community empowerment is encouraged by the Scottish Government, which promotes community ownership and involvement in risk management. Development Trusts and Community Land Acts have emerged as key agents of change, challenging the power of large landowners and redirecting wealth back into local economies. However, the effectiveness of these policies is likely to be based on key individuals and groups within the local community and the level of expertise and time they have. Social capital may indicate the likely levels of effective response. This means that a likely scenario is that though some rural communities will be enabled to develop and access resources, this development is likely to be uneven, with the key being down to local individuals to enact change.

The Scottish Government aims to achieve 20-minute neighbourhoods, where essential services are accessible within 20 minutes, though this is challenging for rural areas. Public transport links between villages are vital for delivering this goal. Rural Policy 3.0, published by OECD, aims to provide rural dwellers with a level of well-being comparable to urban areas, focusing on economic, social, and environmental dimensions. Centralised governance, whether at the level of Scotland or the UK, often fails to cater to rural particularities or is unable to

distribute resources effectively, with local governance struggling to have enough resources and central governance unable to distribute resources effectively.

Driver 4: Environment

Land Use Changes and the Just Transition in rural Scotland

There has been a significant discourse around land use change in rural Scotland. The Scottish Government has a target of achieving 'net-zero' emissions by 2045, and aims to achieve this through a just transition: enacting land use changes that are carried out in a socially just way, with a particular emphasis on the challenges faced by rural communities (McKee et al., 2023: 2-3). To bring about these significant changes, the Scottish Government has incentivised land management approaches such as tree-planting and peatland restoration for carbon sequestration (McKee et al., 2023: 3). This is resulting in a growing trend of green land investment projects across rural Scotland, that can create both opportunities and challenges for communities (McKee et al., 2023: 21). Increasingly, pressure is being applied to policymakers for greater regulation of the natural capital market, and on landowners to ensure a thorough community engagement process (McKee et al., 2023: 67). Rewilding is one activity that can be part of green land investment (McKee et al., 2023: 1) and is associated with ecological restoration, nature conservation, and sometimes the reintroduction of species and limited human interference (Martin et al., 2021:1). The term has attracted much attention, and views on the activities it describes, and its perceived benefits and negative impacts vary greatly. Some people are concerned about the impact that it may have on communities, with the connotations of decreasing human presence, and go so far as to suggest that it represents 'new Clearances' (Martin et al., 2021:1). There has been a dual discourse around rewilding, as a counter to rewilding, but also a recognition that the two do not necessarily have to be mutually exclusive (Martin et al., 2021: 6). Repeopling, referring to the repopulation of vacated areas of rural Scotland, especially in the Highlands and Islands, is a less contentious term, with all interviewees in Dolton-Thornton's (2021:41-42) study, stating their support for repeopling. However, this support came with the qualifications that a robust economy, nearby jobs and a permanent (rather than touristic) population were necessary for enabling repopulation. Interestingly, in Martin et al.'s (2021:6) study, it was suggested that rewilding could actually help with this vision of repeopling, with the suggestion that rewilding would create additional jobs and a more 'sustainable and economically viable use of the land'.

Renewable energy holds a contentious space within the 'rewilding vs repeopling' debate (Dolton-Thornton, 2021: 39). Both conservation Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and the Scottish Government have challenged and restricted the development of renewable energy in 'wild' places, such as the Highlands (Dolton-Thornton, 2021: 39). This stems from arguments that such developments can be unsightly and can ruin the landscape, and from the potential environmental damage caused by building renewable energy facilities. Importantly, the natural environment is often a driving factor for people deciding whether to move to or stay in rural areas, and therefore maintaining the natural

environment also plays a part in maintaining populations (Wilson et al., 2024: 32).

Community level responses to climate change

Scotland is ahead of the rest of the UK in terms of community owned renewable energy developments (Slee, 2024: 7). The Scottish Government has supported community climate change initiatives, with the Climate Challenge Fund offering 100% grants to community groups to aid the delivery of emission reductions within communities (Slee, 2024: 7). This approach is limited in its capacity to deliver landscape scale change, however, as initiatives often fall to key individuals in different communities, and with differences in community capacities, change is rarely even (Slee, 2024:14). The shift towards grassroots responses to climate change has been mirrored in political discourse as individual self-responsibility and local-level flood responses are encouraged (Henderson et al., 2020:226). However, this shift has not coincided with an understanding of the diversity of community capacities (Henderson et al., 2020:226).

The COVID-19 pandemic provided a unique scenario to draw climate issues into sharper focus (Malcolm, Macaulay and Todd, 2024: 6; McIntyre and Roy, 2023: 7). For example, some rural communities reported that the pandemic highlighted the flaws of globalisation, for example the strengths of community growing projects instead of relying on supermarkets (Malcom, Macaulay and Todd, 2024: 6). Tourism also changed during the pandemic. Some rural areas have experienced a sharp increase in visitor numbers over the past 10 years, which has come with associated environmental concerns, such as littering and habitat damage. People in rural areas reported that the COVID-19 pandemic had offered an opportunity to strengthen environmental resilience (McIntyre and Roy, 2023: 7). The ban on travel also meant that the tourism industry effectively stopped during lockdowns, and although the break caused significant economic strain and threatened rural businesses, it also gave local communities the time and space to “catch-up’ on infrastructure priorities at tourist hotspots” (McIntyre and Roy, 2023: 7). Some rural inhabitants were apprehensive about the ending of COVID-19 lockdowns, due to the return of environmental strain caused by tourists, especially in areas with a prominent tourist attraction (McIntyre and Roy, 2023: 7).

Research on land ownership, crofting and cultural heritage projects has revealed strong community connections to land, especially for those who work on and with the land (Heaton, 2023: 4). Community land trusts were also identified as social enterprises that can develop social and emotional ties to land, when they engage in cultural heritage projects (Heaton, 2023: 4). Processes such as these generate social capital within communities, creating a sense of place that has been strongly linked with community well-being (Heaton, 2023: 4).

Transport

Studies have found inadequate public transport provision across rural areas of Scotland. Geographical remoteness in some areas, such as the Highlands, means that public transport provision is not always cost effective which adds to difficulties of provision (Vercher et al., 2021: 176). External stressors, such as extreme weather events and the COVID-19 pandemic can add extra pressure to public transport, for example in workforce availability, and can highlight where there are weaknesses (Maclaren et al., 2024: 6-7). In one study, participants noted that the increased encouragement away from car use necessitates improved and sufficient public transport (Malcolm, Macaulay and Todd, 2024: 7). In efforts towards net zero, electric vehicles are also being encouraged, but some living in rural areas have highlighted that there is a lack of working charging points that makes widespread use difficult (Malcolm, Macaulay and Todd, 2024: 7). The reality of rural living must be fully accounted for, in order to provide appropriate infrastructure.

Recycling, waste disposal, and the circular economy

Recycling and waste disposal can also prove a challenge in remote areas, with less facilities available. For example, the Scottish Islands Survey (2023) highlighted issues faced by those living on islands. In less frequently visited island regions, it was reported that levels of litter were low; however, this level increased on more accessible islands with higher numbers of tourists (Wilson et al., 2024: 32). More remote island regions reported that it was difficult to dispose of large household items, with islands lacking the facilities to do so, and it being awkward to transport such items to the mainland (Wilson et al., 2024: 32).

The circular economy is mentioned in the economy section as a potential method of providing a more sustainable economy for Scotland. Many rural areas however do not have the infrastructure and are not able to follow certain Scotland-wide policies. For example, the infrastructure is not yet there in rural areas to support certain circular economy strategies such as promoting the use of electric cars due to some communities not having enough charging points (Malcolm, Macaulay and Todd, 2024: 7).

Conclusion

This section has focused on Driver 4: Environment. In conclusion, the discourse around land use change in rural Scotland highlights the Scottish Government's commitment to achieving net-zero emissions by 2045 through a just transition. This involves incentivizing land management practices like tree-planting and peatland restoration, which present both opportunities and challenges for rural communities. The concept of rewilding, while controversial, is part of this green investment trend and can potentially coexist with re-peopling efforts to revitalize rural areas. Renewable energy development remains a contentious issue, balancing ecological preservation with the need for sustainable energy sources. Community-level responses to climate change, supported by initiatives like the Climate Challenge Fund, demonstrate Scotland's leadership in community-owned renewable energy projects. However, these efforts are limited by uneven capacities across communities. Strong community connections to land, facilitated

by community land trusts and cultural heritage projects, are crucial for generating social capital and for enhancing community well-being. Addressing transport and infrastructure challenges, such as inadequate public transport and recycling facilities, is essential for supporting rural populations and promoting a circular economy.

Driver 5: Society

Migration decisions

The trend of depopulation in some rural areas partly reflects decisions about migration. Young people play a key role in this trend as they often must either travel or move to an urban area to pursue further education or other training opportunities (Tent et al., 2023: 163). Of those who move away for education or job opportunities, some may return, and some may decide to stay in urban areas. Data from the Scottish Islands Survey demonstrated that younger people (aged 18-35) were mostly likely to return or move to their island after completing education. At the same time, retirement migration to rural areas is also prevalent, as 11% of respondents to the Scottish Islands Survey gave this as a reason for moving to their island, and some other key reasons for people moving or returning to their island were “for a better lifestyle or quality of life”, “to take up a new job”, or “to be close to family” (Wilson et al., 2024: 10-11). In a study by Leith and Sim (2022:6), respondents were most likely to say that their reason for return was for “family or personal reasons.” Other reasons that were mentioned were moving for employment or for their quality of life.

The role of tourism in communities

The importance of tourism in the economy of rural Scotland, its rapid increase in recent years, and concern over extractive forms of tourism are described in the discussion of tourism as an economic driver, summarised above. However, tourism can affect rural communities in much broader ways. It is argued that tourism can affect population structures, with some communities viewing the addition of new people as a key advantage of tourism (White, van Melik and Bendle, 2024) as new people are being introduced to the rural area adding knowledge, ideas and opportunities. Tourism has the benefit of introducing new people to areas where they may form connections and choose to join the community (White, Melik and Bendle, 2024). There is, however, an issue with increasing media presence (through social media, TV, movies, over the internet) on high tourism areas, especially in rural areas where these places are not equipped with the services and infrastructure for the high number of tourists that they get (Garrison and Wallace, 2021). Tourism also is seen to have negative impacts on communities physically through increasing traffic levels, negative environmental impact, the stress on infrastructure and also anti-social behaviour (White, van Melik and Bendle, 2024: 930). Some tourists do not respect rural residents’ communities or local areas which can lead to tensions arising. Research has demonstrated that after COVID-19, an influx of domestic travellers came to rural areas and did not support the local economy or take care of the environment (White, van Melik and Bendle, 2024: 931-2). Vercher et al. (2021:

176-7) note that there is a perception that tourism is being developed without much consultation of the local community. There can also be infrastructural issues that do not allow those visiting tourist sites in a rural area access to the local villages nearby, which can also cause tensions. Organisations like Historic Environment Scotland (HES) are also trying to find ways to solve this issue, including by installing footpaths that have improved tourist access to community amenities (Garrison and Wallace, 2021: 8).

Rural health and wellbeing

Rural areas are currently dealing with the difficulties of reduced services in health and social care occurring at the same time as an ageing population with higher demands on these services. These challenges are made worse due to the difficulties in recruiting and attracting healthcare professionals (Maclaren et al., 2024). The Scottish Government has highlighted the importance of providing health care for rural and remote areas but also recognise that a key difficulty in meeting this priority is staff recruitment and retention (Maclaren et al., 2024: 2). Abelsen et al. (2020: 6) highlight that difficulties with both lack of productivity and staff retention and recruitment can be due to health services in rural areas often being shaped around urban services. Due to the population projections, the health and care services must 'be adapted and maintained'.

Varying levels of wellbeing are experienced in rural Scotland, with some researchers finding rural and island areas to have better wellbeing compared to urban areas (Halliday, Clemens and Dibben, 2022) which can be explained by social cohesion and research that demonstrates that participating and integrating in communities and having a close-knit community can have a positive impact on mental wellbeing. Halliday, Clemens and Dibben (2022: 6) found that mental health is better in islands compared to living on the mainland. One reason for this may be due to the environment that surrounds them, with ready access to nature and green and blue landscapes (Halliday, Clemens and Dibben, 2022: 6).

Other research has found that rural health - especially mental health - is usually worse compared to urban areas (Macaulay, McHugh and Steiner, 2021). These studies suggest that although living in a rural area does not affect direct health outcomes negatively, it is the isolation of living in a rural area that impacts health. Heaton's (2023) literature review identified that some individuals from Scottish Islands have high levels of mental wellbeing (and that connection to land and nature is beneficial for wellbeing), but that there is a variation of wellbeing between those living there. Some residents felt that they had connections with others who used similar mental health services, however felt "differentiated and distanced from the wider community" (Heaton, 2023: 5). Others who were from minority groups felt excluded and socially isolated. There is also apprehension faced when getting support for mental health due to stigma and lack of anonymity in some rural communities (Heaton, 2023).

Technology advancement in healthcare

The COVID-19 pandemic placed a substantial strain on rural health services which in many places were already limited (Atterton and Glass, 2021). It did however allow a shift of more services to be online, which provided a more accessible option to rural residents if they had the correct facilities and skills (Atterton and Glass, 2021). Cowie, Townsend and Saleminck (2020: 172) suggest that technological advances in healthcare are beneficial for rural areas, however, connectivity needs to be improved in rural areas for this to happen. They introduced the term 'Internet of Things' (IoT) which can be used to deliver digital healthcare remotely in rural and remote areas (see more in the Technology section).

Arts and culture

Socialising and engaging in arts and culture play a large role in rural residents' lives. Participants in Dalglish et al.'s (2020: 56) study say that culture in rural communities can assist in business development, employment and help to keep residents in the rural area.

The most recent Scottish Islands Survey (2023) found that islanders participate in many different social and cultural activities. Participation is generally lower among older residents. However, popular activities that islanders take part in are going to a pub, bar or club, attending social community events, attending culturally specific festivals, going to the gym and attending live music events. Islanders were more likely to attend culturally specific festivals compared to residents in mainland Scotland (Wilson et al., 2024: 38).

Festivals can play a role in showcasing Scottish cultural heritage (Gamble, 2022). Rural and island culture are also big pull factors for tourists to visit these areas. For example, a festival in Orkney called St Magnus International Festival attracts both visitors and locals and was reported in 2016 to have created 55 full-time jobs (with almost half of them in Orkney) (Gamble, 2022: 13). Orkney Islands Council has created the Orkney Arts Development Strategy that is working to create more fair jobs in the arts.

Argyll and Bute is another region that has a musical heritage - their traditional music being performed in festivals, pubs, for tourists and in many other locations (McKerrell and Hornabrook, 2021). Unfortunately, like many local authorities, the funds for arts, culture and heritage have been cut in Argyll and Bute. Based on a consultation for the Cultural Assembly there appears to be a 'lack of appreciation' of how culture and heritage can impact the economy (McKerrel and Hornabrook, 2021: 242).

Education

The provision of education services can be difficult in remote areas of Scotland, and population decline is leading to falling school rolls which are projected to continue in future (Sibieta and Snape, 2025), potentially challenging the viability of schools. Despite this, survey evidence from the islands shows a strong satisfaction with the quality of primary school education. Data from the Scottish

Islands Survey (2023) showed that 77% of respondents agreed that there is good quality accessibly primary education for their child. A smaller proportion of respondents (60%) agreed that they have access to good quality secondary education (Wilson et al., 2024: 40).

63% of respondents agreed that in a subject of their choice, islanders could complete a college education, with less respondents agreeing that they could complete a university degree in the subject of their choice (43%). This figure has decreased from the 2020 survey, where 54% of respondents in 2020 agreed that they could complete a university degree (in a subject of their choice) on their island (Wilson et al., 2024: 42). For example, one respondent from Arran, Bute and the Cumbraes agreed that there are good college facilities on their island, but that the course choices are very limited (Wilson et al., 2024: 41).

Post- school educational opportunities

There are many benefits to rural areas for providing access to post-school educational opportunities, including supporting communities to thrive, improving infrastructure and providing local employment opportunities (Tent et al., 2023: 163). Having available educational opportunities also impacts quality of life and plays an important role in young people's decision to stay or leave their area (Tent et al., 2023: 163). These opportunities can also have long term impacts such as the development of new ideas or methods and entrepreneurship, and can lead to the making of new businesses in the area (Tent et al., 2023:163).

An example of a post school educational opportunity in the rural Scottish context is GrowBiz which is an organisation founded in the Perth and Kinross area that provides further training and educational opportunities for rural 'micro businesses' and individuals who would like to start their own business. They offer a variety of learning opportunities through workshops, training sessions and networking opportunities. The companies they support are from varied backgrounds in tourism, the arts and care sectors and the business support offered is varied too - examples are marketing, digital skills and legal issues - but the solutions and advice are all catered around rural experiences (Tent et al., 2023: 166). GrowBiz has digitally expanded out of Perth and Kinross to other rural regions in Scotland. Opportunities like GrowBiz demonstrate prospects for post-school educational resources that are decentralised and accessible to rural areas.

Conclusion

This section focused on Driver 5: Society. In conclusion, the depopulation trend in rural Scotland is significantly influenced by the movement of young people who often leave for education and job opportunities in urban areas. While some return, many choose to stay in cities. Tourism is a key feature of rural

communities. It introduces new people to rural communities, potentially strengthening community identity and activism, though it also brings challenges like increased traffic and environmental stress.

Well-being in rural areas varies, with some studies indicating better mental health due to social cohesion and access to nature, while others highlight the negative impact of isolation. Community engagement in arts and culture plays a vital role in rural life, supporting business development and the retention of residents.

Access to some types of educational opportunities are a concern, with limited access to secondary and higher education on the islands. Addressing these challenges requires a nuanced approach to support the unique needs of rural Scotland and ensure sustainable community development.

Driver 6: Technology

Themes in the literature relating to technology in rural Scotland include connectivity issues faced by those living in rural areas and the divide between rural and urban digitalisation.

Poor Wi-Fi connection

Poor WiFi is frequently mentioned in the literature as a significant challenge faced by those in rural areas of Scotland, with several research studies focused on this specific issue (Cowie et al., 2020; Pant & Odame, 2017; Salemink et al., 2017; Townsend et al., 2013). A particular issue is connectivity speeds, with some rural areas missing out on the most up to date broadband infrastructure due to logistical issues of remoteness and low population density (Noble et al., 2024: 71). Noble et al. (2024) report that broadband connectivity only arrived in one of their rural Scottish case studies during the first COVID-19 lockdown, and some community members remained disconnected due to them living so far away from the broadband exchange that the cost would have been too much to connect them (Noble et al., 2024: 82). Next Generation Broadband (NGB), which can also be referred to as Superfast Broadband, has been rolled out to 91% of UK properties, however in rural areas there is only 66% coverage (Palmer-Abbs, Cottrill and Farrington, 2021: 101). Scotland was the most underserved nation in the UK, with 27% of premises unable to access sufficient broadband speed (Palmer-Abbs, Cottrill and Farrington, 2021: 101). In this study, many of the participants interviewed, reported that they had considered paying privately for NGB or a community satellite package, but found the significant amount of time and cost off-putting (Palmer-Abbs, Cottrill and Farrington, 2021: 105). This results in a growing inequity between rural and urban areas in Scotland.

Academic literature has identified that universal high-speed broadband is critical to rural development, and it enables those who wish to stay and make a living in remote areas to do so, but it has been suggested that this has not been adequately addressed in most countries (Cowie, Townsend and Salemink, 2020: 174). The pandemic highlighted this growing divide between rural and urban broadband access, with the increase in online activity from remote working and

online school lessons (McKerrell and Hornabrook, 2021: 21). This period demonstrated not only connectivity issues, but also a discrepancy in rural digital skills, with some struggling to get online (McKerrell and Hornabrook, 2021: 21). With a generally older population, it is also notable that in rural areas, landline connections remain an important mechanism of communication for older people, and these connections too must be maintained if not improved (Wilson et al., 2024).

This section demonstrates a stark inequality between the development of broadband connectivity and WiFi speeds across urban and rural areas of Scotland and more widely in the UK. Poorer internet access creates particular challenges in rural areas with aging populations.

Policy approaches to evening out digital access

Top-down policy-led approaches seek to address the rural-urban digital divide and issues in broadband connectivity. However, these approaches have been criticized for being overly centralised and therefore failing to address specific localised broadband issues (Palmer-Abbs, Cottril, Farrington, 2021: 101). On the other hand, community-based approaches can create a disproportionate burden on individuals within communities and lead to ‘volunteer ‘burn-out’’, a trend that mirrors the wider community empowerment agenda (Palmer-Abbs, Cottril, Farrington, 2021:101).

One study highlighted that policies should not aim to bring rural areas up to speed with urban areas, but should rather aim to address specific issues within different rural communities, appreciating the heterogeneity of the challenges and needs that they may have (Noble et al., 2024: 82). This includes addressing the needs of specific communities within rural areas such as crofters (Noble et al., 2024: 82). Notably, there is a tension not only between rural and urban areas, but also within rural areas, as some members of the community live so remotely that they are still unable to access the broadband that has been provided, creating an ‘intra-rural digital divide’ (Noble et al., 2024: 82). Therefore, rural areas are not only being left behind as a whole, but also particularly remote dwellings within rural areas are being further cut off from technological advancements. Islands too have varied experiences of digital development and WiFi connections, with main and central isles more likely to be well connected than smaller, outer isles (Wilson et al., 2024). The implications that this has on residents’ ability to work from home is highly important, as limitations to broadband connections also limit the work opportunities available (Wilson et al., 2024).

Technology in Rural Areas

Because of the unique characteristics of rural areas, in some cases, technology can be used to cater to specific rural needs. Public transport is widely recognised as a favourable mode of transport for the environment, however rural and island services are reported as wholly inadequate (Malcolm, Macaulay and Todd, 2024: 7; Wilson et al., 2024: 17). As highlighted above in the Environment section,

electric cars were mentioned in one study as a potential environmentally friendly alternative when sufficient public transport was not available (Malcolm, Macaulay and Todd, 2024:7). However, electric cars need charging stations in order to function: it has been observed that charging stations in one rural area were firstly, not sufficient, and secondly, did not work (Malcolm, Macaulay and Todd, 2024: 7). This demonstrates changes that need to be made in order to provide rural areas with the same sustainable technological solutions as other areas.

Healthcare is another area where technological advancements could aid rural areas. In Cowie's exploration of 'Smart rural futures', the 'Internet of Things' is described as a potential tool to aid rural services (Cowie, 2020: 172). The 'Internet of Things' (IoT) is a term for 'a network of physical objects that are connected, often wirelessly, to wider networks'; the connected objects are not usually things that would be classed as digital (Cowie, 2020: 172). It was suggested that the IoT can offer a way of providing medical care remotely, and it has been suggested as a mode of communicating between community first responders (individuals assigned to respond to emergencies in rural areas) and paramedics, in the case of medical emergencies in remote areas (Cowie, 2020: 172). This would be suitable for the aging population of rural areas and can also save vital time for paramedics attending emergencies in remote rural areas. However, this approach would replace face-to-face interactions with technology instead. In the case of healthcare, especially for potentially socially isolated older people, this may not represent an improvement (Cowie, 2020: 172). This paper also highlights that rural connectivity issues must first be resolved to begin exploring these opportunities (Cowie, 2020: 172); additionally, the rural skills gap mentioned previously may lower the effectiveness of these resources.

Technology advancement

Although many negative experiences and outcomes came from the COVID-19 pandemic, something seen as a positive, long-term outcome is the ability for people to work from home (Currie et al., 2024: 40). Employment opportunities were created, increasing 'community resilience' which has a positive effect on the 'population profile' (Currie et al., 2024: 36-37). Digitalisation is being used to provide services online as it can be more accessible and have a much larger reach to rural and island areas (Currie et al., 2024: 40). There are still, however, difficulties with digitalisation in some businesses due to costs of implementation and lack of technological skills (Noble et al., 2024: 82). It has been suggested that training opportunities such as drop-in sessions and tutorials would be beneficial to small businesses (Noble et al., 2024: 82). Technology can bring more people together who work in similar areas helping drive decision-making and inclusion. However, as this switch has been made online, it has highlighted the divide between rural and urban areas as there can be poor connectivity in many rural areas which inhibits some from being able to be involved in many aspects of the community.

Conclusion

This section focused on Driver 6: Technology. In conclusion, poor WiFi connectivity remains a significant challenge in rural Scotland, exacerbating the digital divide between rural and urban areas. While top-down policy approaches have been criticized for their centralisation, community-based solutions often place undue burdens on individuals. Addressing the specific needs of diverse rural communities is crucial, as some more remote areas remain disconnected despite broader broadband initiatives.

Technological advancements, such as the Internet of Things, offer potential benefits for rural services, but connectivity issues must be resolved first. The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the importance of digitalisation and remote work, which have positively impacted rural employment and resilience. However, the implementation of digital solutions faces challenges related to costs and technological skills. Ensuring equitable access to sustainable technological solutions is essential for the future development of rural Scotland.

Conclusion and Next Steps

The literature review has summarised factors which are currently influencing economic development in rural Scotland, using a framework of six drivers of change. The DEPEST framework has provided an effective way of structuring and presenting this review; however, in reality, many of the largest and most influential challenges and opportunities facing rural Scotland cannot be neatly categorised into those six drivers of change and instead cut across more than one. Reflecting on the DEPEST-structured review above, we have identified some major cross-cutting topics - or 'nexuses of change' (Piras et al., 2022: 960) - which should be priorities for research to understand economic development in rural Scotland. These are summarised below, alongside questions which illustrate a selection of the uncertainties over the future direction of each nexus of change (Table 2).

Table 2: Influential drivers of change in the economy of rural Scotland

Nexus of change	Key questions
Demographic processes affecting rural communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can younger people who leave for post-school education and job opportunities – contributing to an aging population – return to live and work in rural areas in greater numbers than previously? • Will migration into rural areas continue at similar rates in the future, both from the rest of the UK (through, for instance, remote working opportunities) and international migration (historically for jobs in key sectors such as health, care and farming)?
Rural housing, transport and infrastructures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will the availability and affordability of rural housing improve due to private or public investment?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will rural infrastructure and transport decline and suffer from further cuts, or will they improve and develop as a result of increasing investment?
Climate change and economic benefits from transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will rural places gain long-term place-based economic benefits from the just transition – for example, through wealth and jobs created by renewable energy schemes and rewilding initiatives, and through greater wellbeing? • Will the effects of climate change intensify, impacting rural areas more?
Directions of the tourism sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will less extractive, more sustainable and sensitive models of tourism expand, potentially supported by improved tourist infrastructure and new tourist taxation?
Technological changes affecting working patterns, housing, transport and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can technological changes across society (e.g. improved digital connectivity, online healthcare appointments, electric vehicles) support the needs of rural residents, given an aging population, sparsely populated areas and existing digital divides? • Will rural connectivity improve and become more affordable? • Will the phenomenon of remote working persist and/or expand, benefiting rural, island and remote localities?
Community empowerment and centralization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do all rural places have the human and social capital and capacity to play an active role in community planning and the management of local assets? • Will local authorities and the Scottish and UK Governments – operating at larger scales than rural communities – be sensitive to local needs when designing future policies?
National and international events and crises	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic and cost-of-living crisis persist in rural Scotland? • To what extent will additional global events and crises affect the economic and demographic context of rural Scotland? • Will the UK and/or Scotland distance themselves even more from Europe, or start a process of reintegration into the EU?

To conclude, rural Scotland faces a range of challenges and opportunities that require nuanced, place-based approaches to ensure sustainable development

and community well-being. Employment in rural areas is characterized by part-time work, self-employment, and small businesses, with renewable energy potentially offering new job opportunities. However, declining employment prospects and difficulties in recruiting staff, exacerbated by the long-term effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, EU exit and the cost of living crisis, highlight the need for targeted policies.

Depopulation trends are influenced by young people moving to urban areas for education and job opportunities. Tourism is one of the most significant contributors to rural economies, but over-tourism and lack of sufficient infrastructure can make it difficult for some rural and island communities to cope with visitors. Views on the impact of rural residence on well-being vary, with some studies indicating better mental health due to social cohesion and access to nature, while others highlight the negative impact of isolation.

Poor WiFi connectivity in rural areas can exacerbate the digital divide, and addressing specific local needs is crucial. Technological advancements offer potential benefits for rural services, but connectivity issues must be resolved first. The COVID-19 pandemic has underscored the importance of digitalisation and remote work, positively impacting rural employment and resilience. However, this can lead to changes in the structures of rural and island populations and tension between old and new residents.

Community engagement in arts and culture supports business development and retention of residents, while educational opportunities remain a concern. Addressing transport and infrastructure challenges, such as inadequate public transport and recycling facilities, is essential for supporting rural populations and promoting a circular economy. Overall, a holistic, place-based approach is vital for addressing the unique needs of rural Scotland and ensuring a sustainable and equitable future.

Bibliography

[DEPEST]:

Abelsen, B., Strasser, R., Heaney, D., Berggren, P., Sigurðsson, S., Brandstorp, H., Wakegijig, J., Forsling, N., Moody-Corbett, P., Akearok, G. H., Mason, A., Savage, C., & Nicoll, P. (2020). Plan, recruit, retain: A framework for local healthcare organizations to achieve a stable remote rural workforce. *Human Resources for Health*, 18(1), 63.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12960-020-00502-x>

Alexander, R. (2023). Who returns? Understanding experiences of graduate return to rural island communities. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 103, 103112.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2023.103112>

Atterton, J., & Glass, J. (2021). Place-based policies and the future of rural Scotland. https://pure.sruc.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/43749594/Place_based_policies_and_the_future_of_rural_Scotland_OCT_2021_FINAL.pdf

- Brzozowska-Rup, K., & Radowicz, J. A. (2025). Migration to Scotland from the EU8 countries. *Quality & Quantity*, 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-025-02159-x>
- Clarke, R. (2021). Highlands and Islands Enterprise: Managing Depopulation with Long Range Lights. <https://doi.org/10.4422/ager.2021.19>
- Clelland, D. (2020). Beyond the city region? Uneven governance and the evolution of regional economic development in Scotland. *Local Economy: The Journal of the Local Economy Policy Unit*, 35(1), 7–26. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0269094219899917>
- Clelland, D. (2021). In a straightjacket? Targeting deprivation in rural Scotland in the context of localism and austerity. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 83, 155–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2021.02.008>
- Clelland, D. (2024). ‘One central purpose’? Tracking the Evolution of Strategic Approaches to Economic Development in Scotland. *Scottish Affairs*, 33(2), 178–198. <https://doi.org/10.3366/scot.2024.0499>
- Cowie, P., Townsend, L., & Salemink, K. (2020). Smart rural futures: Will rural areas be left behind in the 4th industrial revolution? *Journal of Rural Studies*, 79, 169–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2020.08.042>
- Currie, M., Wilson, R., Noble, C., Hopkins, J., & Marshall, A. (2024). The impact of COVID-19 on the resilience of rural and island Scotland: Implications for transitioning to a resilient rural and island future. *Scottish Geographical Journal*, 140(1–2), 29–48. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14702541.2024.2328274>
- Dalglis, C., Dodds, A., Mackay, D., & Belford, H. (2021). Rural Planning Policy to 2050: Research to Inform Preparation of NPF4. <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/research-and-analysis/2020/01/rural-planning-policy-2050-research-inform-preparation-npf4/documents/rural-planning-policy-2050-research-inform-preparation-npf4/rural-planning-policy-2050-research-inform-preparation-npf4/govscot%3Adocument/rural-planning-policy-2050-research-inform-preparation-npf4.pdf>
- Dolton-Thornton, N. (2021). Rewilding and re-peopling in Scotland: Large-scale land managers’ perspectives and practices. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 86, 36–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2021.05.010>
- Gamble, J. R. (2022). Exploring the Relationship Between Arts Festivals And Economic Development in Rural Island Regions: A Case Study of Scotland’s Orkney Isles. *Event Management*, 26(2), 349–367. <https://doi.org/10.3727/152599521X16288665119486>
- Garrison, S., & Wallace, C. (2021). Media Tourism and Its Role in Sustaining Scotland’s Tourism Industry. *Sustainability*, 13(11), 6305. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13116305>
- Glass, J., Shucksmith, M., Chapman, P., & Atterton, J. (2024). Rural lives during COVID-19: Crisis, resilience and redistributing societal risk. *Scottish Geographical Journal*, 140(1–2), 49–69. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14702541.2023.2237935>
- Goudie, A., Roy, G., & Waite, D. (2024). Scotland’s Economy after 25 Years of Devolution. *Scottish Affairs*, 33(4), 381–405. <https://doi.org/10.3366/scot.2024.0521>

- Gow, K., Currie, M., Duffy, P. M., Wilson, R., & Philip, L. J. (2023). Gow's Typology of Scotland's Islands: Technical notes. https://aura.abdn.ac.uk/bitstream/handle/2164/22333/Gow_etal_Report_Gows_Typology_Scotlands_VOR.pdf?sequence=1
- Halliday, K., Clemens, T., & Dibben, C. (2022). The island effect: Spatial effects on mental wellbeing and residence on remote Scottish islands. *Wellbeing, Space and Society*, 3, 100098. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wss.2022.100098>
- Heaton, J. (2023). Experiences of connectedness and mental wellbeing in the Scottish islands. *Wellbeing, Space and Society*, 5, 100181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wss.2023.100181>
- Henderson, F., Steiner, A., Farmer, J., & Whittam, G. (2020). Challenges of community engagement in a rural area: The impact of flood protection and policy. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 73, 225–233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2019.11.004>
- Islands Growth Deal, Full deal document. (2023). <https://www.islandsdeal.co.uk/downloads/file/44/full-deal-document>
- Leith, M. S., & Sim, D. (2022). 'Will ye no' come back again?': Population challenge and diaspora policy in Scotland. *Population, Space and Place*, 28(7), e2572. <https://doi.org/10.1002/psp.2572>
- Macaulay, B., McHugh, N., & Steiner, A. (2021). Public perspectives on health improvement within a remote-rural island community. *Health Expectations*, 24(4), 1286–1299. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.13260>
- MacKinnon, D., & Derickson, K. D. (2013). From resilience to resourcefulness: A critique of resilience policy and activism. *Progress in Human Geography*, 37(2), 253–270. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309132512454775>
- Maclaren, A. S., Locock, L., Skea, Z., Cleland, J., Denison, A., Hollick, R., Murchie, P., Skåtun, D., Watson, V., & Wilson, P. (2024). 'Moving to the countryside and staying'? Exploring doctors' migration choices to rural areas. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 108, 103210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2024.103210>
- Malcolm, Z., Macaulay, B., & Todd, M. (2024). Towards a circular economy and just transition to net-zero in rural Scotland: Resident perspectives on policy and practice. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 108, 103300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2024.103300>
- Martin, A., Fischer, A., McMorran, R., & Smith, M. (2021). Taming rewilding - from the ecological to the social: How rewilding discourse in Scotland has come to include people. *Land Use Policy*, 111, 105677. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2021.105677>
- McIntyre, S., & Roy, G. (2023). Revisiting the dimensions of rural resilience: The CoVid-19 pandemic. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 103, 103107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2023.103107>
- McKee, A., Beingessner, N., Pinker, A., Marshall, A., Currie, M., & Hopkins, J. (2023). The Social and Economic Impacts of Green Land Investment in Rural

Scotland. <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/research-and-analysis/2023/12/social-economic-impacts-green-land-investment-rural-scotland/documents/social-economic-impacts-green-land-investment-rural-scotland/social-economic-impacts-green-land-investment-rural-scotland/govscot%3Adocument/social-economic-impacts-green-land-investment-rural-scotland.pdf>

McKerrell, S., & Hornabrook, J. (2022). Mobilizing traditional music in the rural creative economy of Argyll and Bute, Scotland. *Creative Industries Journal*, 15(3), 237–256. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17510694.2021.1928420>

Neal, S., Gawlewicz, A., Heley, J., & Jones, R. D. (2021). Rural Brexit? The ambivalent politics of rural community, migration and dependency. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 82, 176–183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2021.01.017>

Noble, C., Townsend, L., Currie, M., Hardy, C., & Duckett, D. (2024). The impacts of COVID-19 on digitalisation and social capital in crofting communities in Scotland. *Scottish Geographical Journal*, 140(1–2), 70–90. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14702541.2023.2259866>

OECD. (2018). Rural 3.0. A framework for rural development. https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2018/03/rural-3-0_fe038f7c/618f702b-en.pdf

Palmer-Abbs, M., Cottrill, C., & Farrington, J. (2021). The digital lottery: The impact of next generation broadband on rural small and micro businesses in the North East of Scotland. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 81, 99–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2020.08.049>

Philip, L., Wilson, R., & Duffy, P. (2024). Rurality, islandness and public policy in Scotland. *Scottish Geographical Journal*, 140(1–2), 113–135. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14702541.2024.2315994>

Scottish Government. (2020). Rural Planning Policy to 2050: Research findings. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/rural-planning-policy-2050-research-inform-preparation-npf4/>

Scottish Government. (2022). Place-based policy approaches to population challenges Lessons for Scotland. <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/independent-report/2022/12/place-based-policy-approaches-population-challenges-lessons-scotland/documents/place-based-policy-approaches-population-challenges-lessons-scotland/place-based-policy-approaches-population-challenges-lessons-scotland/govscot%3Adocument/place-based-policy-approaches-population-challenges-lessons-scotland.pdf>

Scottish Government. (2023). *National Planning Framework 4*. <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/strategy-plan/2023/02/national-planning-framework-4/documents/national-planning-framework-4-revised-draft/national-planning-framework-4-revised-draft/govscot%3Adocument/national-planning-framework-4.pdf>

Scottish Government. (2024). Scotland's Circular Economy and Waste Route Map to 2030. <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/strategy-plan/2024/12/scotlands-circular-economy-waste-route-map-2030/documents/scotlands->

[circular-economy-waste-route-map-2030/scotlands-circular-economy-waste-route-map-2030/govscot%3Adocument/scotlands-circular-economy-waste-route-map-2030.pdf](https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/research-and-analysis/2024/09/scottish-islands-survey-2023-main-findings-report/documents/scottish-islands-survey-2023-main-findings-report/govscot%3Adocument/scotlands-circular-economy-waste-route-map-2030.pdf)

Scottish Human Rights Commission. (2024). Economic, Social and Cultural Rights in the Highlands and Islands. <https://www.scottishhumanrights.com/media/2881/main-report-economic-social-and-cultural-rights-in-the-highlands-and-islands.pdf>

Sibieta, L., & Snape, D. (2025). *Scottish school spending, teachers and pupil numbers* ISF Report. The Institute for Fiscal Studies, London. <https://ifs.org.uk/publications/scottish-school-spending-teachers-and-pupil-numbers>

Slee, B. (2024). Collaborative Action, Policy Support and Rural Sustainability Transitions in Advanced Western Economies: The Case of Scotland. *Sustainability*, 16(2), 870. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16020870>

Stjernberg, M., Norlén, G., Vasilevskaya, A., Tapia, C., & Berchoux, T. (2023). Scoping Report on European Rural Typologies. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13767183>

Tent, N., Syssner, J., Mose, I., & Rennie, F. (2024). Post-school education in shrinking rural regions: Experiences and solutions from Scotland and Sweden. *Raumforschung Und Raumordnung | Spatial Research and Planning*, 82(2), 160–174. <https://doi.org/10.14512/rur.1692>

Vercher, N., Barlagne, C., Hewitt, R., Nijnik, M., & Esparcia, J. (2021). Whose Narrative is it Anyway? Narratives of Social Innovation in Rural Areas – A Comparative Analysis of Community-Led Initiatives in Scotland and Spain. *Sociologia Ruralis*, 61(1), 163–189. <https://doi.org/10.1111/soru.12321>

White, E., Van Melik, R., & Bendle, J. (2024). Perceived Impacts of Tourism on Community Identity: Perspectives of Two Scottish Highland Communities. *Tourism Planning & Development*, 21(6), 917–939. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21568316.2024.2398465>

Wilson, R., Hopkins, J., Bender, F., Manson, L., Currie, M., Martínez Sánchez, G., & Potts, J. (2024). Scottish Islands Survey (2023) Main Findings Report. <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/research-and-analysis/2024/09/scottish-islands-survey-2023-main-findings-report/documents/scottish-islands-survey-2023-main-findings-report/scottish-islands-survey-2023-main-findings-report/govscot%3Adocument/scottish-islands-survey-2023-main-findings-report.pdf>

Wilson, R., Noble, C., & Currie, M. (2025). The changing rural idyll and the ideal migrant: The case of Scotland during COVID-19. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 114, 103497. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2024.103497>

Woods, M. (2023). Rural recovery or rural spatial justice? Responding to multiple crises for the British countryside. *The Geographical Journal*, geoj.12541. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geoj.12541>

Aspirational Scenarios

This section outlines the results of a separate literature review which focused on recent policies and strategies published by nationwide and regional organisations which could be pertinent to rural economic development, and their stated aims and objectives. It then proposes a series of aspirational scenarios developed from the key drivers and policies that emerged from the relevant papers.

The organisations which have published the policies and strategies reviewed here include the Scottish Government, regional development and planning bodies (Highlands and Islands Enterprise, South of Scotland Enterprise, the Cairngorms and Loch Lomond and the Trossachs National Parks), and Regional Growth Deal partnerships.

This review identifies targets and claims of economic development at the national and regional scales. The key metrics and information accompanying these, including the numbers of jobs supported or created and evidence of industries or places which are likely to benefit and/or receive investment, and other aims or 'aspirations' of relevant interventions, are recorded in a structured format.

This policy review builds on key themes drawn out in the above literature review, focusing on significant issues facing rural areas, rather than aiming to address the breadth of the current policy landscape in Scotland.

Methodology

Key policy documents were found through the Scottish Government website, using 'rural' as a key word to filter relevant papers. We also conducted specific searches for specific place-based documents, such as Community Place Plans and Regional Growth Deals.

Key publications were recorded in a spreadsheet, and screened. Documents that covered more general plans and visions, without giving specific goals or identifying metrics were discarded, and plans and papers that stated specific statistics and goals were prioritised. Notably, relatively few articles stated specific aspirational statistics, and therefore the initial document base was significantly reduced. Where specific goals were stated, these were recorded and categorised into the DEPEST categories – Demography, Economy, Policy and Governance, Environment, Society, and Technology.

To produce the aspirational scenarios, we gathered similar policies under key driver areas linked to each DEPEST category. Key drivers were largely identified through the literature review. Using a combination of the stated policies, we have proposed a series of aspirational scenarios for each key driver. These aspirational scenarios are based on the assumption that the policies and goals stated will be successfully implemented.

Demography

Issue addressed: Population maintenance (youth)

Rural and island areas are currently experiencing youth out-migration, with young people moving out of rural areas to seek jobs and further education (due to the lack of suitable and well-paid jobs and post-education opportunities). Once having moved and completed further education, young people often experience difficulties when returning to their rural area due to the lack of housing and suitable jobs available. To address this issue, rural and island areas are working to provide educational opportunities and affordable and available housing to allow and encourage young people to stay, maintaining young people in their population.

Key policies:

Cairngorms National Partnership – Skills and training

- Aims to develop a green skills / a youth apprenticeship project, along with scholarships and a scheme to mentor young people who wish to work at the National Park (Cairngorms National Park Partnership Plan, 2022-27: 58).

Rural and Islands Housing Action Plan

- By 2032, the Scottish Government & Rural and Islands Action Plan will deliver 110,000 affordable homes, of which 10% will be in remote, rural and island communities (Rural & Islands Housing Action Plan, 2023: 3).

Housing to 2040 – Rural and island communities

- In the four years leading to March 2020, 4,800 affordable homes were delivered to rural and island communities. The next phase will continue to provide affordable homes for the communities. Communities will also be supported with the Rural and Islands Housing fund after March 2021 (Housing to 2040, 2021: 27-28).

The Inverness and Highland City-Region Deal

- This deal will aid in rebalancing the population (Inverness and Highlands City Region Deal, 2017: 5):

Well-paid jobs will be created with estimates that the deal will create 6,000 new houses over 20 years (1,000 being affordable homes).

The deal aims to retain/attract an additional 1,500 people between the ages of 18-29 in the 10-year deal period

The deal will create 1,125 direct jobs as a result from projects, adding a further 2,200 construction jobs too

The Inverness and Highland City-Region Deal - Housing

- "£5 million towards a programme of mid- market rent property to create more new homes which will be initially targeted at young people (Inverness and Highlands City Region Deal, 2017: 10).

The Inverness and Highland City-Region Deal - Housing

- Partners of the Deal (2017: 9) will work together to "explore innovative approaches to delivering skills and employability programmes across the Highlands."

The Inverness and Highland City-Region Deal – Science Skills Academy

- The Scottish Government will provide funding (£3m) to create learning centres for science, technology, engineering, mathematics and digital creativity (STEMD). "The hubs will raise engagement for young people, closely link employers with their potential workforce and will foster long term relationships with young people with an interest and aptitude for these disciplines" (Inverness and Highlands City Region Deal, 2017: 9)

Issue addressed: Creating affordable and available housing

Rural and Island areas currently face a shortage of affordable and available housing (partly due to homes being bought for the purpose of holiday lets that are often empty for multiple months of the year due to the off-season). This limits the number of people planning to move to rural areas. Young people and those of working age are particularly affected by the lack of housing as it limits people moving to the area to take up essential jobs. Rural and island areas are working to provide more suitable and affordable housing opportunities, which will allow people to move to the island to take up work and allow those who cannot afford current housing the opportunity to stay in their rural or island area.

Key Policies:

Housing to 2040 – Rural and island communities

- In the four years leading to March 2020, 4,800 affordable homes were delivered in rural and island communities. The next phase will continue to provide affordable homes for the communities. Communities will also be supported with the Rural and Islands Housing fund (£30 million investment) after March 2021. (Housing to 2040, 2021: 27/28).
- Housing to 2040 will "take action so that rural and island communities have access to high quality, affordable and market housing which has been planned alongside economic and physical infrastructure and helps people to live, work and thrive - and we will help to stem rural depopulation" (Housing to 2040, 2021: 5).
- Setting a longer-term ambition Scotland-wide to deliver a further 100,000 affordable homes up to 2032. "It is our aim that at least 70% of those homes will be for social rent, helping to tackle poverty and homelessness" (Housing to 2040, 2021: 17).
- "Improve the condition and quality of existing properties, including agricultural tenancies and tied accommodation, through the new Housing Standard" (Housing to 2040, 2021: 29).

Scottish Programme for Government: Equality, Opportunity, Community – Preventing and ending homelessness and supplying affordable, safe homes

- The Scottish Programme for Government (2023:31) will invest £752 million through the Affordable Housing Supply Programme to continue to create more affordable homes to meet housing needs and the target of 110,000 affordable

homes by 2032 - at least 70% will be available for social rent and 10% will be available in rural and island communities.

The Inverness and Highland City-Region Deal

- Partners "estimate that the City-Region Deal will create 6,000 new houses over 20 years, of which 1,600 will be affordable homes" (Inverness and Highlands City Region Deal, 2017:5).

The Inverness and Highland City-Region Deal – Housing

- "£5m towards a programme of mid-market rent property to create more new homes which will be initially targeted at young people (Inverness and Highlands City Region Deal, 2017:10).

Aspirational Scenario 1:

Young people will have the ability to stay in their rural or island area to attend post educational opportunities including apprenticeships, mentorships, courses around STEM, and courses that develop both green and digital skills

Aspirational scenario 2:

Young people will have the ability to return or stay in rural and island areas as there will be more job opportunities allowing the working age population to grow.

Aspirational scenario 3:

More affordable homes will be delivered to rural and island areas which will reverse the depopulation trends that are currently being observed in rural and island areas. There will be affordable homes (for example through mid-market rent in Highland and Island areas) for young people and those working to move in to.

Aspirational Scenario 4:

Housing will be provided to low-income families and those facing homelessness through social and mid-market rent opportunities, meeting a wider range of socio-economic needs.

Economy

Issue addressed: Tourism

Tourism plays a key role in the rural economy, providing many jobs and boosting communities' local economies. Tourism can be a point of contention in some rural areas, with many communities concerned that there is a lack of infrastructure in their local area for tourists. Policies have been created to support the tourism sector to become more sustainable, place-based and to create more opportunities for visitors to come and support the local economy.

Key Policies:

Ayrshire Growth Deal – Tourism Programme

- "The Scottish Government will provide investment of up to £9 million for the development of The Great Harbour, at Irvine Harbourside and Ardeer, alongside an additional £5 million from North Ayrshire Council, to create a unique coastal destination comprising a number of key assets to attract new visitors to the area and create jobs" (Ayrshire Regional Growth Deal document, 2020: 20).
- "The Scottish Government will invest up to £9.5 million in Marine Tourism, delivering critical infrastructure to enable investment to secure the development of the Marine Tourism industry in North Ayrshire. This investment will focus on securing infrastructure that supports key components such as sailing and boating, marine leisure, and recreation" (Ayrshire Growth Deal document, 2020: 20).

Islands Growth Deal – Spaceport 1

- The SG will invest up to £1m to support Spaceport 1, which "aims to respond to the growing market of suborbital launch related activities, by building a modest and adaptable launch facility at Solpaig Farm site (North Uist)." The Islands Deal investment will "support the development of a fully serviced launch facility for the suborbital market, providing a launch pad and permanent facilities and utilities tailored to the specific needs of launch operations." This will provide economic benefit to Uist, by 2025 it will employ 25 people, it will also provide training opportunities (Islands Growth Deal, 2023: 23).

Highlands and Islands Enterprise Strategy- Tourism

- "Support the sector to transition to net zero and ambition to be a recognised sustainable visitor destination" (HIE Strategy, 2023: 20).
- "Contribute to strong place-based tourism partnerships with industry, communities and the public sector to manage investment and destination planning" (HIE Strategy, 2023: 20).

Argyll and Bute Rural Growth Deal – Tourism - Creating a World Class Visitor Destination

- "The proposal is to open up access to Argyll's coasts and waters to develop Argyll as a West of Scotland "must visit" location for the maritime leisure market. There is a clear opportunity for Argyll to become Scotland's prime destination for the marine leisure market, for private craft, charter yachts and

cruise ship passengers to come ashore and for land-based visitors to gain access to the water on boat excursions and for water sports, wildlife watching and to island hop" (Argyll and Bute Rural Growth Deal, 2021:4).

Aspirational Scenario 1:

Investors will support the restoration and creation of attractions (The Great Harbour; Spaceport 1; Argyll's coastline) that will encourage visitors to come to rural and island areas, contributing to the rural economy and communities.

Aspirational Scenario 2:

The tourism sector will be supported in making the transition to Net Zero and become place-based, allowing for more sustainable tourism in rural Scotland.

Issue addressed: Employment

Some rural areas are currently seeing a decline in employment and career opportunities. Research shows the difficulties faced by young people in accessing job opportunities due to a lack of jobs with good incomes or progression opportunities. To address this, more job opportunities are being created across rural Scotland in a variety of different sectors.

Key Policies:

Islands Growth Deal – Our Deal

- The Islands Deal investments aim to improve economic productivity, deliver up to 1,300 jobs by 2032, and support the islands to be among the first places in the UK to achieve net zero (Islands Growth Deal, 2023: 7).

Highlands and Islands Enterprise Strategy- Marine Energy

- Marine energy will create 4,000 jobs by 2030 (HIE Strategy 2023:19).

The Inverness and Highland City-Region Deal

- This Deal (2017: 5) will create an estimate of an additional 1,125 direct jobs through the projects with a further 2,200 additional jobs in the construction sector.
- The Inverness and Highlands City-Region Deal (2017: 5) estimates that the deal will "help to skill up the labour market and contribute towards a high skilled wage economy" and "improve productive and real wages, which are estimated to increase by an additional 1.3% and bring an additional £100m per annum to the regional economy."

The Inverness and Highland City-Region Deal – Transport

- Road safety improvements and reduced journeys on 'key strategic routes' for the A82, A9 and A96. "The improvements will increase accessibility to jobs,

education and healthcare" (Inverness and Highlands City-Region Deal, 2017: 10).

The Inverness and Highland City-Region Deal - UHI School of Health and Life Science

- The University of Highlands and Islands School of Health & Life Science's initiative "will address issues with the innovation and commercialisation of health and care products and services"
- The "commercialisation of new products and services and business growth are expected to lead to at least 70 additional high-value full time equivalent jobs in the region. In addition, co-investment in business development from venture capital providers and other private and public sector sources could provide around £14m in addition to the £9m investment through the City-Region deal" (Inverness and Highlands City-Region Deal, 2017: 8).

Aspirational Scenario 1:

A range of new jobs will be created in rural and island areas, in different sectors such as marine energy, construction, health and care services etc.

Aspirational Scenario 2:

Roads in rural areas will be improved, helping to improve connectivity and accessibility of jobs.

Aspirational Scenario 3:

Fair wages will be implemented across sectors in rural and island areas.

Policy and Governance

Due to the nature of this policy review, aspirational policies and governance are captured throughout this report. Therefore, in this section, the focus is on place-based policies, a strong theme that emerged in the literature review as both an opportunity and challenge for rural areas.

Issue Addressed: Place-based Policies

The direction of travel in Scotland at the moment is towards place-based policies that aim to empower communities to enact change at a local level. This can create opportunities for local people to steer change, however, it is notable that it can also place a burden on key individuals in rural areas and cause volunteer burn-out. Current policies demonstrate the move towards a place-based approach and recognise the importance of community voices.

Key Policies:

Housing to 2040

- “Ensure that we take a place-based approach and reflect a sound understanding of the aspirations of rural communities. People living and working in rural areas are best placed to help decide how their communities can grow in a way that meets their needs and so it is essential they are involved in planning their future development” (Housing to 2040, 2021: 29).
- “Invest £325 million over five years in community-led regeneration, community wealth building and town centre revitalisation” (Housing to 2040, 2021: 21).
- “Put more focus on place in our housing programmes, using the Place Principle and a Place Investment Framework” (Housing to 2040, 2021: 21).
- “Deliver a rolling programme of demonstrator locations to help illustrate what future Town Centre Living and 20 minute neighbourhoods can look like” (Housing to 2040, 2021: 21).
- “Provide support for local authorities to use the new £50 million Vacant and Derelict Land Investment Programme” (Housing to 2040, 2021: 21).

Aspirational Scenario:

Rural communities are given powers and, critically, sufficient resources, to enact change locally. This includes financial support for local authorities and creating mechanisms to enable rural people to create tangible change in their own communities.

Environment

Issue addressed: Transitioning to renewable energy.

Scotland is currently working towards a Just Transition, the process by which Scotland will become net zero by 2045 in such a way that will bring benefits to people and the environment. As a part of the effort towards this, several organisations' plans and policies are working towards implementing new renewable energy initiatives in Scotland. Several plans refer specifically to rural areas; islands too are highlighted in efforts to enable island entities to become more self-sufficient.

Key Policies:

Powering Change, calling the South of Scotland into Action

- South of Scotland to be a carbon negative region by 2045, powered by sustainable energy (South of Scotland Enterprise, 2021a: 5).

Highlands and Islands Enterprise Strategy- Marine Energy

- 4,000 jobs in marine energy will be created by 2030 (HIE strategy, 2023:19).

Islands Growth Deal – Dales Voe Ultra-Deep Water Quay

- The Dales Voe Ultra-Deep Water Quay, set to be developed in Shetland, has received investment of up to £9 million from Scottish Government. It has been identified as the “optimal location in the UK for an ultra-deep water decommissioning facility due to its sheltered approach”. This presents opportunities for offshore wind and will create “100 jobs that will be sustained for the next 25 years” (Islands Growth Deal, 2024:18).

Islands Growth Deal – Shell-volution

- “The Shell-volution project has been designed as a new and innovative technical programme enabling future growth in the low-carbon and sustainable mussel farming sector in Shetland.” This is set to increase productivity, efficiency and resilience, while developing new locations too. Employment supported by the sector is set to increase by 50%. The project is led by the University of the Highlands and Islands (Islands Growth Deal, 2023: 22).

Islands Growth Deal – Outer Hebrides Energy Hub

- Investment of £11 million from the UK government to support the Outer Hebrides Energy Hub which “will be a Green Hydrogen Production, Storage and Distribution Facility, which will, by 2030, supply Green Hydrogen for 100% conversion of the Scotland Gas Network’s (SGN’s) Stornoway Town Centre Propane network.” The facility will then be scaled up to produce green hydrogen for community use (Islands Growth Deal, 2023: 17).

Housing to 2040 - Affordable warmth and zero emissions homes

- “By 2045, emissions from heating all buildings need to reach zero. The type of heating used in over 2 million homes and 100,000 non-domestic buildings must be changed by 2045 and we estimate that around 50% of homes, or over 1 million households, will need to convert to a low or zero emissions heating system by 2030” (Housing to 2040, 2021:43).

Aspirational Scenario 1:

All regions of Scotland will be carbon negative by 2045. Buildings across Scotland will have zero heating emissions.

Aspirational Scenario 2:

New technology and infrastructure will provide new forms of renewable energy and offer more efficient methods of transitioning to renewable energy.

Aspirational Scenario 3:

Jobs in the sectors of renewable energy and sustainable technology will be increased and provide sustainable employment opportunities.

Issue addressed: Protecting Biodiversity

Alongside a Just Transition, the Scottish Government is also striving to enhance and protect biodiversity in Scotland. 30 by 30 is a global initiative that states the aim of protecting 30% of terrestrial and marine areas by 2030, a UN Convention that has been agreed upon by 196 states, including Scotland (NatureScot, 2024). The policies below illustrate efforts to enhance habitats and protect biodiversity, using approaches such as reforestation and peatland restoration; consequential benefits to wellbeing and the economy are noted.

Key Policies:

Nature Scot – Framework for 30 by 30 in Scotland

- By 2030 at least 30% of Scotland’s land (including terrestrial, inland water and coastal habitats) will be protected or conserved for biodiversity, delivering for people and climate (NatureScot, 2024: 11).

The National Islands Plan – Strategic Objective 8: ‘To improve and promote environmental wellbeing and deal with biosecurity’

- Part of this objective is the plan “to protect island biodiversity” and to “address biosecurity in a holistic and integrated manner as a means not only to contribute to environmental wellbeing, but also to contribute to sustainable economic development on Scottish islands” (The National Islands Plan, 2019:52).

Loch Lomond and the Trossachs, National Park Partnership Plan – Restoring Nature

- “More than treble the average annual rate of peatland restoration from 240ha to 840ha, achieving at least 5900ha by 2030” (Loch Lomond and the Trossachs – National Park Partnership Plan, 2024: 129).
- “Double the average annual rate of woodland expansion from 200ha to 400ha, focusing on priority areas” (Loch Lomond and the Trossachs – National Park Partnership Plan, 2024: 129).

Scottish Programme for Government: Equality, Opportunity, Community – Environment and Forestry

- “Restore 10,700 hectares of degraded peatland and progress action with crofters to support more peatland restoration on crofting land, including the Scottish Ministers’ crofting estates, as well as commencing the process to ban the sale of horticultural peat for domestic use” (Scottish Programme for Government, 2023:47).

Aspirational Scenario 1:

That 30% of Scotland’s land and marine areas are designated as protected areas by 2030 and are being managed in such a way as to protect and enhance biodiversity. This includes actions such as tree planting and peatland restoration.

Aspirational Scenario 2:

Management for biodiversity in such a way that promotes environmental well-being and sustainable economic development in rural areas of Scotland.

Issue addressed: Circular Economy

Working towards more sustainable and self-sufficient communities in Scotland includes coming up with innovative ways to provide resources to rural communities sustainably. Policies aimed at enabling a circular economy in Scotland are emerging as a way to address this issue.

Key Policies:

The National Islands Plan – Strategic Objective 8: ‘To improve and promote environmental wellbeing and deal with biosecurity’

- The National Islands Plan will “establish an islands forum, through Zero Waste Scotland, as part of the implementation of the Deposit Return Scheme, to ensure that key considerations for islands (and rural communities more generally) are reflected. This Forum will support, not only, input into our legislative plans for the scheme but also ensure that key considerations for islands communities are integrated into the implementation planning process” (The National Islands Plan, 2019:52).
- “Work with island communities to explore how they can contribute to the circular economy through small-scale pilots for example supporting local food production (The National Islands Plan, 2019:52)”.

The National Islands Plan – Strategic Objective 9: ‘To contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation and promote clean, affordable and secure energy’

- “Work with island communities to look at alternative solutions to managing waste, particularly in respect of Scotland’s Circular Economy Strategy” (The National Islands Plan, 2019:57).

Aspirational Scenario:

Circular economy tools are successfully implemented into rural communities with the help of rural forums which integrate rural and island voices. Resources are provided to enable alternative solutions to waste management.

Issue addressed: Transport

Transport in rural areas is key for connectivity to essential services. Recent research has demonstrated significant shortcomings in rural public transport provision, that must be addressed in order for residents of rural areas to travel both locally, nationally and internationally. There are also significant efforts in Scotland to transition to more sustainable modes of transport, and the following policies demonstrate these efforts, along with goals of easing rural travel.

Key Policies

Loch Lomond and the Trossachs, National Park Partnership Plan – Creating a Low Carbon Place

- “Reduce transport emissions from travel to and from the National Park by at least 61% from the 2019 baseline by 2030” (Loch Lomond and the Trossachs – National Park Partnership Plan: 130).

The Inverness and Highland City-Region Deal - Transport

- “The Inverness and Highland City-Region Deal will support the development of the A9/A96 Inshes to Smithton Link Road which will improve the operation of the network for longer distance and local journeys, providing relief to the A96 east of Inverness and the Raigmore junction” (The Inverness and Highlands City-Region Deal, 2017: 10).

The Inverness and Highland City-Region Deal – Inverness Air Access

- “Local partners have identified the importance of ensuring continued air access for the economic development of the region, in particular business-friendly daily links to international hubs and adequate interlinking connections. Maintaining and improving the level of air access to London is the top priority for local partners over the longer term. In addition, a daily rotation to the international hub Amsterdam Schiphol Airport is also a priority” (The Inverness and Highlands City-Region Deal, 2017: 11).

National Transport Strategy- Takes climate action

- “Public bodies taking the lead by working towards phasing out petrol and diesel cars from the public sector fleet and also phase out the need for any new petrol and diesel light commercial vehicles by 2025” (National Transport Strategy, 2020: 50).
- “The ambition to phase out the need for new petrol and diesel cars and vans in Scotland by 2032” (National Transport Strategy, 2020: 50).
- “Plans to decarbonise Scotland’s passenger railways by 2035. Where electrification isn’t feasible or it is not appropriate to do so, there will be

investment in battery-powered trains and work with developers of hydrogen fuel cell trains to accelerate their development and deployment through practical trials in Scotland” (National Transport Strategy, 2020: 50).

- “Work to decarbonise scheduled flights within Scotland by 2040” (National Transport Strategy, 2020: 50).

Aspirational Scenario 1:

Road connections between rural areas and city hubs will be improved to take the strain off particularly busy areas.

Aspirational Scenario 2:

Public and private transport emissions will be reduced; new petrol and diesel cars will be phased out by 2032; work will be done to decarbonise passenger railway services by 2035 and decarbonise flights within Scotland by 2040.

Aspirational Scenario 3:

Ensure that air travel to London and abroad remains accessible to those travelling from island and remote areas to especially enable business-friendly travel.

Society

Issue addressed: Healthcare

Rural Scotland has an ageing population, and as a result there is an increasing demand for healthcare and therefore a strain on current healthcare. Rural areas also have difficulties in recruiting and retaining staff and there are also further difficulties for rural residents to access healthcare due to the distances some have to travel to access GP's, specialist services and hospitals. Policies are addressing these issues by providing more healthcare jobs, creating digital healthcare opportunities and addressing current issues in healthcare such as backlogs.

Key Policies:

The Inverness and Highland City-Region Deal – Assisted Living

- "The Inverness and Highland City-Region Deal will support the development of clusters of innovative assisted living schemes at key locations in the region. These new homes will be designed with full IT health and movement sensors linked to remote health and care providers, building on the existing Telehealth capability and supporting future developments in Telehealth" (Inverness and Highlands City Region Deal, 2017: 8).
- Providing that there is the approval of the business case, the SG "will provide up to £3 million towards an initial five clusters of eight assisted living homes that would be built in different parts of the Highlands. This funding will leverage further investment from partners including Housing Association investment of £2,224,000" (Inverness and Highlands City Region Deal, 2017: 8).
- Residents will be provided with tailored, 'responsive care and health packages' which "monitor their conditions as required. This will enable elderly people to continue to live in their communities and help avoid the need for hospitalisation or residential care" (Inverness and Highlands City Region Deal, 2017: 8).

National Workforce Strategy for Health and Social Care in Scotland – Health and Social Care Recovery

- Backlogs in healthcare will be addressed and £29m will be invested to target 'diagnostic backlogs.' This will provide opportunities for additional procedures which will rise to 90,000 per year from 2025/26 (National Workforce Strategy for Health and Social Care in Scotland, 2022: 19).
- Capacity in healthcare will be increased by at least 10%, and to do this the NHS workforce will grow over the next 5 years by 1% (1,800 whole time equivalent). "This will be in addition to projected required growth, ensuring there is a workforce capacity to address backlogs and increase capacity in the NHS" (National Workforce Strategy for Health and Social Care in Scotland, 2022: 18).
- Investment (more than £400m) will be increased in National Treatment Centres to contribute to delivering over 40,000 additional surgeries and procedures per year. To help support this, 1,500 additional staff will be

recruited (both domestic and international) (National Workforce Strategy for Health and Social Care in Scotland, 2022: 19).

- £23m will be delivered to redesign urgent care. This will allow fast access to clinicians via digital technologies (telephone or video consultation) where possible, providing the ability to support people 'to be cared for in the right place by the right person' (National Workforce Strategy for Health and Social Care in Scotland, 2022: 21).

Aspirational scenario 1:

Digital health infrastructure will allow people in rural and island areas to access fast-paced health advice when needed

Aspirational scenario 2:

Healthcare backlogs will be addressed, which provides the opportunities for more procedures to take place each year.

Aspirational scenario 3:

More jobs around healthcare will be created which will increase the working population in rural and island areas and also means that there will be more staff to provide healthcare to patients, which is necessary for the ageing population in rural areas.

Issue addressed: Providing education and skills development opportunities

In rural areas there is a lack of education and skills development opportunities past secondary school education, often leading to young people leaving their rural area once they have completed school. To combat this issue, policies have been created to fund campus redevelopments, provide further education opportunities along with skills development and placement opportunities.

Key Policies:

Islands Growth Deal – Thriving, Sustainable Communities

- The Island Growth deal have plans in place for campus redevelopments (Orkney, Shetland and the Outer Hebrides) (Islands Growth Deal, 2023: 25-26).

The Inverness and Highland City-Region Deal – Northern Innovation Hub

- The Northern Innovation Hub "will provide tailored support for high growth of small and medium sized businesses as well as encouraging new starts." This will include providing 12 graduate 'technology based' placements each year and also the opportunity for shorter summer placements for students around technology (Highland and Islands City Region Deal, 2017: 7).

The Inverness and Highland City-Region Deal – UHI School of Health and Life Science

- The University of Highlands and Islands School of Health and Life Science "will address issues with the innovation and commercialisation of health and

care products and services." Through this a minimum of 70 high-value jobs will be created in the region. Co-investment will be "integrated into the overall UHI School of Health, with complementary funding for teaching, research, sector engagement and commercialisation totaling more than £20m" (Highland and Islands City Region Deal, 2017: 8)

Ayrshire Regional Growth Deal – Economic Infrastructure Programme

- "The Centre of Excellence will be the focus within the AMIC area and will establish Ayrshire as the go-to region for smart manufacturing and digital skills. The innovation centre will be delivered in partnership with Strathclyde University and will focus on Food or Drink innovation from concept to launch" (Ayrshire Regional Growth Deal, 2020: 19).

Argyll and Bute Rural Growth Deal – Rural Schools Accelerator Programme

- "This deal will drive future inclusive economic growth and tackle inequality with a strong focus on community wealth building, STEM skills, rural enterprise and the delivery of local education services. The Rural Skills Accelerator Programme is a vehicle that will provide the 21st century infrastructure and delivery mechanisms needed for skills, training, education and enterprise to facilitate collaborative growth in the rural economy" (Argyll and Bute Rural Growth Deal, 2021:5).

Moray Growth Deal - Early Years STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths)

- 'Specialist facilities and learning environments' will be provided to eight Associated School Groups within Moray "to facilitate STEM learning, positively changing attitudes towards STEM and over time, the culture around how STEM is perceived in the region. These facilities will have core learning equipment focused on early years that will be updated periodically and allow inter-generational learning to take place. The expectation is that these innovative facilities will then attract further industry and sectoral investment that would allow the offering to be expanded to other groups of learners. The intention of the project is to address rurality as a barrier to participation in STEM activities" (Moray Growth Deal, 2021: 21).

Aspirational Scenario 1:

Work placement opportunities will be created for both graduates and students in rural areas that will allow young people to return or stay in their island area, learning practical skills and applying their knowledge in a workplace setting.

Aspirational Scenario 2:

Rural areas will have the infrastructure to provide local education and skills development opportunities across rural areas in Scotland. Rural areas will have the facilities and staff to educate students in Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) subjects and digital skills.

Technology

Issue addressed: Rural Digital Connectivity

One of the areas in which rural areas of Scotland seem to be significantly left behind is in digital connectivity. Advancements in WiFi provision and infrastructure that have happened in other areas of the UK have developed more slowly in rural Scotland. Although there has been more development since the Covid-19 pandemic, it is notable that development has not been even across rural Scotland. Many areas, especially more remote areas and islands do not have sufficient digital connectivity.

Key Policies:

A Changing Nation, How Scotland will Thrive in a Digital World – No One Left Behind

- “We will continue to invest in future-proofed infrastructure through the Scottish 4G infill programme and work collaboratively with the UK Government to ensure maximum impact from the up to £1bn Shared Rural Network (SRN) investment in Scotland – the UK government has said this scheme will provide 91% geographic coverage by at least one mobile network operator” (Scottish Government, 2021a: 31).
- “£600 million investment through the Reaching 100% (R100) programme will continue to deliver future-proofed and resilient broadband infrastructure in some of the most rural areas of Scotland” (Scottish Government, 2021a: 28).

The National Islands Plan – Strategic Objective 6: ‘To improve digital connectivity’

- To do this the National Islands Plan will “Mandate the delivery of gigabit-capable connectivity to selected island locations, through the R100 programme, with many other island communities to benefit once contracts are finalised” (The National Islands Plan, 2019: 43).
- “Call on the UK Government to prioritise early investment in Scotland’s islands as part of their plans for full fibre roll-out by 2025” (The National Islands Plan, 2019: 43).

Housing to 2040 – A new Housing Standard

- “We have committed £600 million to the Reaching 100% broadband programme. This programme will ensure that every home and business across Scotland will be able to access superfast broadband by the end of 2021. We are also investing to improve mobile coverage by funding new masts in selected rural “notspots” via the £25 Million Scottish 4G Infill Programme” (Housing to 2040: 68).

Aspirational Scenario 1:

91% geographic coverage will be provided by at least one mobile network operator. New masts will provide mobile coverage to identified “notspots” in rural Scotland.

Aspirational Scenario 2:

The Reaching 100% programme will deliver resilient broadband infrastructure to some of the most rural areas of Scotland. Every home and business in Scotland will be able to access superfast broadband.

Issue addressed: Building digital skills

Remote working in rural areas presents an opportunity for repopulation of some rural communities. However, it has been noted in some research studies that there is a rural skills gap, due to a lack of resources in rural areas, and the generally older population. Recognising that home-working can offer an opportunity for working age populations to stay in or move to rural areas has resulted in policies that work to further enable this.

Key Policies:

A Changing Nation, How Scotland will Thrive in a Digital World – Digital Education and Skills

- Digital Education and Skills will: “ensure digital knowledge and skills has a place in education; build a skilled digital workforce; support upskilling and reskilling opportunities; increase diversity in the digital skills pool; establish the Scottish Digital Academy as the skills provider of choice; establish a resource of digital and data experts that the public sector can call upon; create a Data Science Competency Centre” (Scottish Government, 2021a: 18).

A Changing Nation, How Scotland will Thrive in a Digital World – Helping all Businesses to Become Digital Businesses

- Helping all Businesses to Become Digital Businesses will: “enable Small and Medium sized Enterprises (SMEs) to adopt and optimise new and resilient digital technologies; expand expert support for SMEs; increase diversity and work with industry to tackle digital skills shortages; collaborate with the tech industry to demonstrate and deliver the benefits of home working” (Scottish Government, 2021a 2021: 19).

The National Islands Plan – Strategic Objective 6: ‘To improve digital connectivity’

- “Develop a digital skills programme designed by island communities to meet their needs” (The National Islands Plan, 2019:43).
- “Extend the availability of coding clubs and community-based digital inclusion programmes across the islands” (The National Islands Plan, 2019: 43).

Aspirational Scenario 1:

The creation of a digitally skilled rural population through training opportunities and education. This will create a more diverse digital skills pool and enable rural communities to gain skills needed to work in the digital workforce.

Aspirational Scenario 2:

Enabling small businesses to become digitally resilient will allow more rural businesses to thrive and meet the needs of the digitally evolving world. This can be done through expert support and training programmes on how businesses can adopt new technologies.

An Aspirational Scenario for Scotland based on the current Policy Landscape

Scotland will prioritise digital innovation, sustainability, population maintenance, and community empowerment in its rural and island regions. This transformation will be driven by initiatives that enhance digital skills, business resilience, connectivity, healthcare, transportation, environmental sustainability, and housing.

Rural communities will become digitally proficient through extensive training and education, creating a diverse and capable workforce. Small businesses will adopt new technologies with expert support, becoming more resilient and competitive. Improved mobile coverage and superfast broadband will bridge the digital divide, fostering economic growth, by allowing a remote-working workforce in rural areas.

Young people will have ample opportunities for a range of work placements, allowing them to stay or return to their communities. Digital health infrastructure will provide quick access to health advice, reducing backlogs and creating more healthcare jobs to support the ageing population of many rural communities.

Transportation will see significant improvements, with better road connections and efforts to reduce emissions. This includes phasing out petrol and diesel cars, decarbonising rail services, and maintaining accessible air travel for business needs. New roads will provide easier connections between rural areas and essential facilities easing travel and pressure on local services.

Rural areas will implement circular economy practices, with sufficient funding provided, enabling community led change. By 2030, a significant portion of Scotland's land and marine areas will be protected, allowing for biodiversity protection and enhancement. The country will be carbon negative by 2045, with new renewable energy technologies providing sustainable employment and energy to residents of Scotland.

Communities will have the power and resources to drive local changes, supported by financial aid and mechanisms for community-driven initiatives. Job creation in various sectors, improved roads, and fair wages will enhance the quality of life in rural areas.

Tourism will thrive with the restoration of attractions, contributing to the rural economy. The sector will transition to Net Zero, promoting sustainable tourism.

More affordable homes will be built, to aid the reversing of depopulation trends and providing housing for low-income families and those facing homelessness.

Young people will have access to educational opportunities and job prospects, allowing them to stay or return to rural areas. Affordable housing options will support this, ensuring a strong working-age population.

This vision portrays a future where Scotland's rural and island communities are digitally advanced, economically resilient, environmentally sustainable, and socially inclusive, ensuring a high quality of life for all residents

Bibliography

Note: references in the text refer to the policy names.

[Aspirational Scenarios]

Argyll and Bute Council, UK Government, & Scottish Government. (2021). *Argyll and Bute Rural Growth Deal, Argyll the Natural Choice, Heads of Terms Agreement*. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/argyll-and-bute-rural-growth-deal-heads-of-terms-agreement/>

Cairngorms National Park. (2022). *Cairngorms National Park Partnership Plan 2022-27*. <https://cairngorms.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Cairngorms-National-Park-Partnership-Plan-full-version-FINAL.pdf>

Highlands and Islands Enterprise. (2023). *Highlands and Islands Enterprise Strategy 2023-28*. [hie-strategy-2023-28-final-031023.pdf](https://www.hie.co.uk/strategy-2023-28-final-031023.pdf)

HM Government, The Highland Council, & Scottish Government. (2017). *Inverness and Highlands City Region Deal*. <https://www.highland.gov.uk/cityregiondeal>

Loch Lomond and The Trossachs National Park. (2024). *National Park Partnership Plan 2024-2029*. [NPPPP-2024_RGB.pdf](https://www.lochlomondandthetrossachs.gov.uk/nppp-2024-2029-rgb.pdf)

NatureScot. (2024). *Framework for 30 by 30 in Scotland*. <https://www.nature.scot/doc/framework-30-30-scotland#what-is-30-by-30>

Orkney Islands Council, Shetland Islands Council, Scottish Government, UK Scottish Government, & Comhairle nan Eilean Siar. (2023). *Islands Growth Deal (full deal document)*. <https://www.islandsdeal.co.uk/downloads/file/44/full-deal-document>

Scottish Government. (2021a). *A changing nation: How Scotland will thrive in a digital world*. <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/strategy-plan/2021/03/a-changing-nation-how-scotland-will-thrive-in-a-digital-world/documents/a-changing-nation-pdf-version/a-changing-nation-pdf-version/govscot%3Adocument/DigiStrategy.FINAL.APR21.pdf>

Scottish Government. (2021b). *Housing to 2040*.

<https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/strategy-plan/2021/03/housing-2040-2/documents/housing-2040/housing-2040/govscot%3Adocument/housing-2040.pdf>

Scottish Government. (2022a). *National Workforce Strategy for Health and Social care in Scotland*. <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/strategy-plan/2022/03/national-workforce-strategy-health-social-care/documents/national-workforce-strategy-health-social-care-scotland/national-workforce-strategy-health-social-care-scotland/govscot%3Adocument/national-workforce-strategy-health-social-care-scotland.pdf>

Scottish Government. (2022b). *Scottish Government—Scotland's National Strategy for Economic Transformation (2022)*. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scotlands-national-strategy-economic-transformation/>

Scottish Government. (2023a). *Equality, Opportunity, Community. Our Programme for Government*.

<https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/strategy-plan/2023/09/programme-government-2023-24/documents/equality-opportunity-community-programme-government/equality-opportunity-community-programme-government/govscot%3Adocument/equality-opportunity-community-programme-government.pdf>

Scottish Government. (2023b). *Rural and Islands Housing Action Plan*. [Rural & Islands Housing Action Plan](#)

Scottish Government. (2019). *The National Islands Plan—Plana Nàiseanta nan Eilean*.

<https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/strategy-plan/2019/12/national-plan-scotlands-islands/documents/national-islands-plan-plana-naiseanta-nan-eilean/national-islands-plan-plana-naiseanta-nan-eilean/govscot%3Adocument/national-islands-plan-plana-naiseanta-nan-eilean.pdf>

Scottish Government, UK Government, & Moray Council. (2021). *Moray Growth Deal, Full deal document*. [https://mymoray.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/MGD - Full Deal Document v9.1 Final with MS sig.pdf](https://mymoray.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/MGD_-_Full_Deal_Document_v9.1_Final_with_MS_sig.pdf)

South of Scotland Enterprise. (2021a). *Powering Change Calling the South of Scotland to Action*. [powering-change-calling-the-south-of-scotland-to-action-final.pdf](#)

South of Scotland Enterprise. (2021b). *Regional Economic Strategy*. [south-of-scotland-regional-economic-strategy.pdf](#)

South of Scotland Enterprise. (2022). *Digital Strategy*. [sose-digital-strategy.pdf](#)

Early Years STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths)

South of Scotland Enterprise. (2023). *Our Five Year Plan 2023-28*. [our-five-year-plan.pdf](#)

Transport Scotland. (2020). *National Transport Strategy, Protecting climate and improving lives*. <https://www.transport.gov.scot/media/47052/national-transport-strategy.pdf>

UK Government, Scottish Government, & Ayrshire Growth Deal. (2020). *Ayrshire Growth Deal document*.

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5fb55758e90e0720978b1a76/20.11.17_AG_D_Deal_Document_-_FINAL.pdf